

UNIVERSITY DUISBURG-ESSEN

FACULTY OF MATHEMATICS

MASTER THESIS

**Non-Smooth Optimization of the
Conditional Value-at-Risk**

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Abstract

In this thesis we consider a stochastic optimization problem involving the Conditional Value-at-Risk as a risk measure. This risk measure is equivalently formulated as a non-smooth minimization problem, which is then discretized by using samples from the underlying probability distribution. A primal-dual algorithm is developed to solve the original problem. This algorithm is implemented in MATLAB and a numerical analysis is carried out with two examples motivated by portfolio optimization and power plant operation planning, respectively.

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1 Introduction

Many optimization problems that are motivated by real world applications include uncertainties, which require us to make decisions without knowing their full effects in advance. These applications can be the optimization of an investment portfolio (cf. [Section 4.1](#)), the planning of power plant operations (cf. [Section 4.2](#)), inventory management, and facility planning – to name just a few.

Different approaches have been developed to model these uncertainties such that their impact on present decision-making can properly be taken into account. One of these approaches is called *stochastic programming* (cf. [Section 2.2](#)). The main characteristic of a stochastic programming problem is its dependence on the availability of probability distributions of the underlying stochastic parameters. These distributions can be used, for example, to compute the expected value of some random variable that is included in the objective function.

However, only considering the expected value might be insufficient sometimes. In these cases a broader view is desirable in order to take deviations from the mean into account. This can be achieved by including risk measures into the objective function (cf. [Section 2.2.3](#)). The particular risk measure treated in this thesis is called *Conditional Value-at-Risk* (CVaR, cf. [Section 2.3](#)), which is also known as *Average Value-at-Risk*, *Mean Excess Loss*, *Expected Shortfall*, *Expected Tail Loss*, etc. Its definition involves the *Value-at-Risk*, which is, for a given probability level β , the lowest amount α such that, with probability β , the loss* will not exceed α . The β -CVaR is the conditional expectation of the losses greater than α .

The Value-at-Risk has some undesirable mathematical characteristics such as a lack of sub-additivity and convexity (cf. [\[RU00, Chapter 1\]](#)). Therefore, it is widely known that CVaR is a superior risk measure compared to VaR since it is coherent, positively homogeneous, and convex (cf. [\[RU00, Chapter 1\]](#)) – to name just a few of its properties. One key feature of CVaR is that it can be determined as the minimum of a convex and continuously differentiable function (cf. [Theorem 2.3.3](#)). When working with a finite set of samples instead of probability distributions, this function becomes piecewise linear but is not differentiable anymore (cf. [Page 12](#)).

At this point, the fields of convex analysis (cf. [Section 2.1](#)) and non-smooth optimization can help minimizing the aforementioned function. One approach is, for example, the non-smooth optimization method of the discrete gradient, which is described in [\[BB06\]](#). Another approach is addressed in this thesis. It uses the primal-dual algorithm introduced by Chambolle and Pock (cf. [\[CP11\]](#)) to solve the optimality conditions (cf. [Section 3.2](#)), which are formulated with the help of subdifferentials and proximal point mappings. This algorithm involves the Euclidean projection of a point onto the so called *bounded probability simplex*, which is a major part of this thesis and addressed in [Section 3.3](#).

The results are implemented in MATLAB and tested with two examples. In [Section 4.1](#), a portfolio optimization model is used to check if the developed algorithm works properly and to get an impression on how the choice of parameters affects the solution process. [Section 4.2](#) describes a model motivated by power plant operation planning and shows how the algorithm behaves if the number of variables/constraints becomes big.

The thesis is concluded with remarks on further research based on the presented results.

*The terms *loss* and *loss-function* are used for the argument of the risk measure and indicate its role in an application framework.

2 Preliminaries

In this chapter we present all essential results from convex analysis and stochastic programming that we will use throughout this thesis. Even though the proofs are not repeated here, they can be found in the respective sources that are mentioned together with the results.

2.1 Convex Analysis

This section is based on the notes [Cla17] to the lecture *Nonsmooth Analysis and Optimization* by Christian Clason. In the whole section we consider a normed vector space X .

At first, we want to recall that a proper function $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}} := \mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}$, where *proper* means $\text{dom}(F) := \{x \in X \mid F(x) < \infty\} \neq \emptyset$, is called *convex* if all $x, y \in X$ and $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ satisfy

$$F(\lambda x + (1 - \lambda)y) \leq \lambda F(x) + (1 - \lambda)F(y).$$

The following lemma shows through which operations we can construct convex functions.

Lemma 2.1.1 (Construction of Convex Functions, cf. [Roc70, Part I, §5]) Let X and Y be normed vector spaces and $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be convex. Then the following functions are convex as well:

- (i) αF for all $\alpha \geq 0$;
- (ii) $F + G$ for a convex $G : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$;
- (iii) $F \circ A$ for $A : Y \rightarrow X$ linear;
- (iv) $x \mapsto \sup_{i \in I} F_i(x)$ with $F_i : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ convex for all $i \in I$ and an arbitrary set I .

If we want to minimize a differentiable function, we have the well known necessary first order optimality condition to find local minimal points by setting the first derivative equal to zero. If the considered function is instead not differentiable, there is no first derivative and we have to work around this issue by using a more general construct than differentiation.

Definition 2.1.2 (Convex Subdifferential) For a function $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ and $x \in \text{dom}(F)$, the convex subdifferential of F with respect to x is defined as

$$\partial F(x) := \{x^* \in X^* \mid \langle x^*, \tilde{x} - x \rangle_X \leq F(\tilde{x}) - F(x) \quad \forall \tilde{x} \in X\},$$

where X^* is the dual vector space of X and $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_X : X^* \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the duality pairing. An element $\xi \in \partial F(x)$ is called *subgradient*.

With this definition we can now formulate the following theorem, which is a generalization of the mentioned first order optimality condition for differentiable functions.

Theorem 2.1.3 (Optimality Condition, cf. [Cla17, Theorem 4.3]) Let $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ and $\bar{x} \in \text{dom}(F)$. Then the following statements are equivalent:

- (i) $0 \in \partial F(\bar{x})$;
- (ii) $F(\bar{x}) = \min_{x \in X} F(x)$.

Note that convexity of F is not required to prove this theorem. Therefore, the condition $0 \in \partial F(\bar{x})$ characterizes the global minimizers of any function F .

Since this optimality condition is the starting point of many non-smooth optimization algorithms, it is reasonable to develop some rules that will make it easier to calculate the subdifferential of the composition of two functions. For example, we will use the following sum rule in Chapter 3, where the objective function is indeed a sum of two functions.

Theorem 2.1.4 (Sum Rule, cf. [Cla17, Theorem 4.8]) Let $F, G : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be convex and $x \in \text{dom}(F) \cap \text{dom}(G)$. Then,

$$\partial F(x) + \partial G(x) \subset \partial(F + G)(x)$$

with equality if there exists an $x_0 \in \text{dom}(F)^\circ \cap \text{dom}(G)$.

Note that, for any subset $U \subset X$, we denote the set of all interior points (i.e. in terms of the norm on X) of U by U° .

The chain rule is another theorem that will help us formulate the optimality conditions in Chapter 3. Let Y be another normed vector space and $L(X, Y)$ the space of bounded linear functionals $A : X \rightarrow Y$. For any $A \in L(X, Y)$, the *adjoint operator* $A^* \in L(Y^*, X^*)$ is defined as

$$\langle A^* y^*, x \rangle_X = \langle y^*, Ax \rangle_Y \quad \forall x \in X, y^* \in Y^*, \quad (2.1.1)$$

where $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_X$ and $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_Y$ are the duality pairings and X^* and Y^* the dual spaces of the respective vector spaces X and Y .

Theorem 2.1.5 (Chain Rule, cf. [Cla17, Theorem 4.9]) Let $A \in L(X, Y)$, $F : Y \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be convex, and $x \in \text{dom}(F \circ A)$. Then,

$$\partial(F \circ A)(x) \supset A^* \partial F(Ax) := \{A^* y^* \mid y^* \in \partial F(Ax)\}$$

with equality if there exists an $x_0 \in X$ satisfying $Ax_0 \in \text{dom}(F)^\circ$.

The so-called *Fenchel-Legendre transformation* allows us to use an equivalent expression of the optimality condition in Theorem 2.1.3 (i), as we will see in Lemma 2.1.10. This is useful if the subdifferential of this transformation is easier to calculate than the subdifferential of the original function. In order to understand this lemma, we first need to define the *Fenchel conjugate*, which is named after the German mathematician Werner Fenchel*.

Definition 2.1.6 (Fenchel Conjugate) Let $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be proper. We define the Fenchel conjugate of F as

$$F^* : X^* \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}, \quad x^* \mapsto F^*(x^*) := \sup_{x \in X} (\langle x^*, x \rangle_X - F(x)).$$

*http://www.math.ku.dk/th/fenchel_w/

If we consider a function $F : X^* \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$, i.e. F is defined on the dual space of X , the Fenchel conjugate is defined as

$$F^* : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}, \quad x \mapsto F^*(x) := \sup_{x^* \in X^*} (\langle x^*, x \rangle_X - F(x^*)). \quad (2.1.2)$$

With this convention, the *biconjugate* $F^{**} := (F^*)^*$ is again defined on X rather than $X^{**} \supset X$, even if X is not reflexive (i.e. $X^{**} \neq X$). The following theorem shows that the biconjugate is, under certain assumptions, equal to the original function.

Theorem 2.1.7 (Fenchel-Moreau-Rockafellar, cf. [Cla17, Theorem 5.1 (i) and (iii)])

Let $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be proper. Then,

$$F^{**}(x) \leq F(x) \quad \forall x \in X$$

with equality if and only if F is convex and lower semi-continuous.

Before we come to the mentioned equivalent optimality condition, we take notice of the following rule that allows us to calculate the Fenchel conjugate of a function, which is multiplied by a constant factor. The proof is straightforward and only uses the properties of the supremum.

Lemma 2.1.8 (cf. [Cla17, Lemma 5.3 (i)]) Let $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be proper. Then,

$$(\alpha F)^* = \alpha F^* \circ (\alpha^{-1} \text{Id})$$

for any $\alpha > 0$ where Id denotes the identity function.

Note that F^* is always convex (cf. [Cla17, Lemma 3.5 (v)]) and lower semi-continuous (cf. [Cla17, Lemma 2.2 (v)]), and proper if F is bounded from below by an affine functional. In order to recall the definition of lower semi-continuity, we first introduce the concept of weak convergence: A sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset X$ converges weakly to $x \in X$, denoted by $x_n \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} x$, if

$$\langle x^*, x_n \rangle_X \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle x^*, x \rangle_X \quad \text{for all } x^* \in X^*. \quad (2.1.3)$$

Note that, if X is a finite-dimensional space, the notions of (strong) convergence and weak convergence coincide (cf. [Kes09, Proposition 5.1.3]).

Definition 2.1.9 (Lower Semi-Continuity) Let $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ and $x \in X$. If F satisfies

$$F(x) \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} F(x_n)$$

- (i) for every sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset X$ with $x_n \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} x$, it is called *lower semi-continuous in* $x \in X$;
- (ii) for every sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset X$ with $x_n \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} x$, it is called *weakly lower semi-continuous in* $x \in X$.

The following lemma shows the connection between a function, its Fenchel conjugate, and their respective subdifferentials.

Lemma 2.1.10 (cf. [Cla17, Lemma 5.5]) Let $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be proper, convex, and lower semi-continuous. Then the following statements are equivalent for any $x \in X$ and $x^* \in X^*$:

- (i) $\langle x^*, x \rangle_X = F(x) + F^*(x^*)$;
- (ii) $x^* \in \partial F(x)$;
- (iii) $x \in \partial F^*(x^*)$.

In the case that we want to avoid calculating the subdifferential, we can use the proximal point mapping (cf. Definition 2.1.11) to find an equation that implicitly defines a subgradient (cf. Lemma 2.1.12). From now on, X is not only a normed vector space but also a Hilbert space (i.e. a Banach space together with an inner product). This enables us to identify the dual space X^* with X by considering the respective Riesz representations (cf. [Cla17, Theorem 1.12]).

Definition 2.1.11 (Proximal Point Mapping) Let $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be proper, convex, and lower semi-continuous and $\|\cdot\|_X$ the norm on X . The proximal point mapping of F is defined as

$$\text{prox}_F : X \rightarrow X, \quad x \mapsto \text{prox}_F(x) := \operatorname{argmin}_{z \in X} \left(\frac{1}{2} \|z - x\|_X^2 + F(z) \right).$$

With the following lemma we have an equivalent expression of the relation in Lemma 2.1.10 (ii). As mentioned before, this will help us find the solution to an optimization problem if we do not explicitly know the subdifferential but are able to calculate the proximal point mapping instead.

Lemma 2.1.12 (cf. [Cla17, Lemma 6.9]) Let $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be proper, convex, and lower semi-continuous, and $x, x^* \in X$. Then, for any $\sigma > 0$,

$$x^* \in \partial F(x) \iff x = \text{prox}_{\sigma F}(x + \sigma x^*).$$

We conclude with some useful calculation rules regarding the proximal point mapping.

Lemma 2.1.13 (cf. [Cla17, Lemma 6.12]) Let $F : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be proper, convex and lower semi-continuous. Then,

- (i) for $\lambda \neq 0$ and $z \in X$ we have with $H(x) := F(\lambda x + z)$ for all $x \in X$ that

$$\text{prox}_H(x) = \lambda^{-1} \left(\text{prox}_{\lambda^2 F}(\lambda x + z) - z \right);$$

- (ii) for $\sigma > 0$ we have that

$$\text{prox}_{\sigma F}(x) = x - \sigma \text{prox}_{\sigma^{-1} F}(\sigma^{-1} x);$$

- (iii) for a proper, convex and lower semi-continuous $G : Y \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ and $\sigma > 0$ we have for all $x \in X, y \in Y$, with $H(x, y) := F(x) + G(y)$, that

$$\text{prox}_{\sigma H}(x, y) = \begin{pmatrix} \text{prox}_{\sigma F}(x) \\ \text{prox}_{\sigma G}(y) \end{pmatrix}.$$

2.2 Stochastic Programming

In this section we give a short introduction to the general framework of stochastic programming. Some expressions from the fields of probability and measure theory are used without comprehensive explanation because this would go beyond the scope of this thesis. However, the interested reader is referred to the respective references.

2.2.1 Uncertainty

The main difference between deterministic and stochastic programming problems is the uncertainty in the parameters of a stochastic program. In an application, this can be for example the return of a financial instrument or the amount of wind energy produced during the day ahead. This uncertainty is modeled as random variables on a probability space.

Definition 2.2.1 (Random Variable) Let $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ be a probability space, i.e. Ω is a non-empty set, $\mathcal{F} \subset 2^\Omega$ a σ -algebra (*set of events*) and $\mathbb{P} : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ a probability measure.

- (i) A measurable function $\hat{z} : \Omega \rightarrow E$, where (E, \mathcal{A}) is a measurable space, is called *random variable*.
- (ii) A vector of n random variables ($n \in \mathbb{N}$) is called *random vector*.

Since it is sufficient for this thesis to consider only real-valued random variables, we assume from now on that $E = \mathbb{R}$ and $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{B}_{\mathbb{R}}$ is the Borel σ -algebra. The vector space of all measurable functions $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P}) \rightarrow (\mathbb{R}, \mathcal{B}_{\mathbb{R}})$ is denoted by $L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$. All random variables/vectors in this thesis will be denoted by hatted letters. For further insight into the theory of probability spaces and random variables, we refer to the specialized literature, e.g. [Kle13].

2.2.2 Two-Stage Stochastic Program

Let $\hat{\xi} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})^d$ be a random vector for some dimension $d \in \mathbb{N}$. Stochastic programming problems are often modeled as two stages (cf. [BL11, Chapter 2.3]):

1. On the first stage, a number of so-called *first-stage decisions* has to be taken before uncertainty is disclosed, i.e. before the realization of the random vector $\hat{\xi}$ is known. These decisions are represented by the vector x .
2. On the second stage, a number of decisions or *recourse actions* can be taken after uncertainty is disclosed. They are called *second-stage decisions* and represented by the vector $y := y(\omega)$, which depends on the random event $\omega \in \Omega$.

We start with the mathematical description of a linear two-stage problem and then extend this formulation to general two-stage problems. Following [SDR09, Chapter 2], a linear two-stage problem can be modeled as

$$\min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1}} c^\top x + \mathbb{E} \left[Q \left(x, \hat{\xi} \right) \right] \quad (2.2.1a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } Ax = b, \quad (2.2.1b)$$

$$x \geq 0, \quad (2.2.1c)$$

where $m_1, n_1 \in \mathbb{N}$, $c \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1}$, $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m_1 \times n_1}$, $b \in \mathbb{R}^{m_1}$ and $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$ denotes the expected value of a random variable. The mapping $Q \left(x, \hat{\xi} \right) : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1}$ a random variable such

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that $Q(x, \hat{\xi})(\omega)$ is the optimal value of the second-stage problem (cf. (2.2.4)) for realization $\omega \in \Omega$, which involves the following variables:

$$\hat{q} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})^{n_2}, \quad (2.2.2a)$$

$$\hat{h} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})^{m_2}, \quad (2.2.2b)$$

$$\hat{T} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})^{m_2 \times n_1}, \quad (2.2.2c)$$

$$\hat{W} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})^{m_2 \times n_2}, \quad (2.2.2d)$$

with $n_2, m_2 \in \mathbb{N}$. The random vector $\hat{\xi} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})^d$ with $d := n_2 + m_2(1 + n_1 + n_2)$ is defined as

$$\hat{\xi} = \left(\hat{q}^\top, \hat{h}^\top, \hat{T}_1, \dots, \hat{T}_{m_2}, \hat{W}_1, \dots, \hat{W}_{m_2} \right)^\top, \quad (2.2.3)$$

where \hat{T}_i and \hat{W}_i denote the i -th row of \hat{T} and \hat{W} , respectively. \hat{W} is often referred to as *recourse matrix* and \hat{T} as *technology matrix*. The second-stage problem for realization $\omega \in \Omega$ can then be written as

$$\min_{y \in \mathbb{R}^{n_2}} \hat{q}(\omega)^\top y \quad (2.2.4a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \hat{T}(\omega)x + \hat{W}(\omega)y = \hat{h}(\omega), \quad (2.2.4b)$$

$$y \geq 0. \quad (2.2.4c)$$

Note that this formulation still allows for some of the random variables in (2.2.2) to be deterministic in the sense that, for example, $\hat{W}(\omega) = W$ for almost every $\omega \in \Omega$ and a matrix $W \in \mathbb{R}^{m_2 \times n_2}$, where *almost every* $\omega \in \Omega$ means $\mathbb{P} \left[\left\{ \omega \in \Omega \mid \hat{W}(\omega) \neq W \right\} \right] = 0$.

In the following chapters of this thesis, we do not want to be restricted to linear models. Thus, we need to generalize this framework. For every $x \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1}$, let $\hat{z}_x \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ be a random variable such that $\hat{z}_x(\omega)$ is, for realization $\omega \in \Omega$, the optimal value of the second-stage problem

$$\min_{y \in \hat{\mathcal{G}}(x)(\omega)} \hat{g}(x, y)(\omega). \quad (2.2.5)$$

Here, $\hat{\mathcal{G}}(x) : \Omega \rightarrow 2^{\mathbb{R}^{n_2}}$ is a random variable for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1}$ and $\hat{g}(x, y) : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a random variable for every tuple $(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_2}$. The entire problem is then given by

$$\min_{x \in X} \mathbb{E}[\hat{z}_x], \quad (2.2.6)$$

where $X \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_1}$ is the feasible set.

The linear two-stage problem (2.2.1) can be formulated in the above form with

$$\hat{g}(x, y)(\omega) := c^\top x + \hat{q}(\omega)^\top y, \quad (2.2.7)$$

$$\hat{\mathcal{G}}(x)(\omega) := \left\{ \tilde{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_2} \mid \hat{T}(\omega)x + \hat{W}(\omega)\tilde{y} = \hat{h}(\omega), \tilde{y} \geq 0 \right\}, \quad (2.2.8)$$

$$\text{and } X := \{ \tilde{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1} \mid A\tilde{x} = b, \tilde{x} \geq 0 \}, \quad (2.2.9)$$

for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1}$, $y \in \mathbb{R}^{n_2}$, and almost every $\omega \in \Omega$.

The following theorem allows us write the two stages of the problem as one.

Theorem 2.2.2 (Equivalent Problem, cf. [SDR09, Theorem 2.20]) The two-stage problem (2.2.6) is equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{x \in X, \hat{y} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})^{n_2}} \quad & \mathbb{E} [\hat{g}(x, \hat{y}(\cdot))] \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \hat{y}(\omega) \in \hat{\mathcal{G}}(x)(\omega) \quad \text{for almost every } \omega \in \Omega, \end{aligned}$$

where $\hat{g}(x, \hat{y}(\cdot))$ denotes for every $x \in X$ the mapping $\Omega \ni \omega \mapsto \hat{g}(x, \hat{y}(\omega))(\omega)$.

If $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_S\}$ is finite ($S \in \mathbb{N}$), every random variable $\hat{y} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})^{n_2}$ can be identified with a vector $(y_1, \dots, y_S) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_2 S}$. The problem in Theorem 2.2.2 can then be written as

$$\min_{x \in X, y_1, \dots, y_S \in \mathbb{R}^{n_2}} \quad \sum_{s=1}^S p_s \hat{g}(x, y_s)(\omega_s) \quad (2.2.10a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad y_s \in \hat{\mathcal{G}}(x)(\omega_s) \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, S\}, \quad (2.2.10b)$$

where $p_s := \mathbb{P}[\{\omega_s\}]$ for all $s \in \{1, \dots, S\}$. This formulation can also be useful if we do not know the distributions of the involved random variables but have instead a set of sample values together with associated probabilities.

2.2.3 Risk Aversion

In the previous section we have only discussed two-stage stochastic optimization problems in which the objective function is defined as the expected value of a random variable (cf. (2.2.6)). This is reasonable if the *Law of Large Numbers* (cf. [Kle13, Chapter 5]) can be invoked and our major concern is the long-term performance. However, this approach does not consider fluctuations of specific outcome realizations. This could cause, for example, the loss of all invested money in a portfolio optimization problem. Therefore, we need to extend the model from the previous section by the capability of measuring and minimizing risk.

Let $\hat{z} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ be a random variable. According to [SDR09, Chapter 6.2], the main idea of a so-called *mean-risk model* is to characterize the uncertain outcome of \hat{z} by two scalars: the expected value $\mathbb{E}[\hat{z}]$ and the risk in form of a risk/dispersion measure $\mathbb{D}[\hat{z}]$. These two objectives are combined to one objective function of the form

$$\mathbb{E}[\hat{z}] + \gamma \mathbb{D}[\hat{z}], \quad (2.2.11)$$

where the coefficient $\gamma \geq 0$ can be varied in order to change the weight of the risk measure, i.e. the price of risk. By minimizing this objective function for a variety of values of γ , we generate a set of so-called *efficient* solutions. These solutions have the property that they, on the one hand, minimize the value of the risk measure for a given expected value, and, on the other hand, minimize the expected value for a given value of the risk measure.

If we use this approach to incorporate a risk measure into the general two-stage problem introduced in Section 2.2.2, problem (2.2.6) becomes

$$\min_{x \in X} \mathbb{E}[\hat{z}_x] + \gamma \mathbb{D}[\hat{z}_x], \quad (2.2.12)$$

for a $\gamma \geq 0$.

Although there is a large variety of risk measures (cf. [SDR09, Chapter 6.2]), we will focus on one particular measure called *Conditional Value-at-Risk*, which is introduced in the following section.

2.3 Conditional Value-at-Risk

In this chapter we first formally define the Conditional Value-at-Risk (CVaR) and then explore some of its crucial properties we will use in the course of this thesis.

2.3.1 Definition

The subsequent definition is based on both [RU00, Chapter 2] and [SDR09, Chapter 6.2.4].

Let $\hat{z} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ be a real-valued random variable. We assume that the distribution of \hat{z} has a density $p_{\hat{z}} : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ (cf. [Kle13, Definition 1.106]). Later we will interpret the value $\hat{z}(\omega)$ for realization $\omega \in \Omega$ as a loss and refer to \hat{z} as the *loss-function* in order to emphasize its role in an application framework. The probability of \hat{z} not exceeding a threshold $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ is given by the distribution function $F_{\hat{z}} : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ of \hat{z} , defined by

$$\alpha \mapsto F_{\hat{z}}(\alpha) := \mathbb{P}(\{\omega \in \Omega \mid \hat{z}(\omega) \leq \alpha\}) = \int_{-\infty}^{\alpha} p_{\hat{z}}(z) dz. \quad (2.3.1)$$

$F_{\hat{z}}$ is non-decreasing and continuous from the right, and we assume for simplicity that it is also continuous from the left. In accordance with the informal definition in Chapter 1, we define the Value-at-Risk as follows.

Definition 2.3.1 (Value-at-Risk) For a given probability level $\beta \in (0, 1)$, the β -VaR of $\hat{z} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ is defined as

$$\text{VaR}_{\beta}(\hat{z}) := \min \{ \alpha \in \mathbb{R} \mid F_{\hat{z}}(\alpha) \geq \beta \},$$

where $F_{\hat{z}}$ is the distribution function of \hat{z} as defined above.

Since $F_{\hat{z}}$ is continuous and non-decreasing, $\text{VaR}_{\beta}(\hat{z})$ turns out to be the left endpoint of the non-empty interval consisting of the values α such that $F_{\hat{z}}(\alpha) = \beta$. Note that this interval might contain more than a single point (cf. [RU00, Page 5]). It follows that the probability of the event $\{\omega \in \Omega \mid \hat{z}(\omega) \geq \text{VaR}_{\beta}(\hat{z})\}$ is equal to $1 - \beta$. This justifies the following definition of the Conditional Value-at-Risk[†] as the conditional expectation of the loss-function relative to the loss being greater than or equal to $\text{VaR}_{\beta}(\hat{z})$.

Definition 2.3.2 (Conditional Value-at-Risk) For a given probability level $\beta \in (0, 1)$, the β -CVaR of $\hat{z} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ is defined as

$$\text{CVaR}_{\beta}(\hat{z}) := (1 - \beta)^{-1} \int_{z \geq \text{VaR}_{\beta}(\hat{z})} z p_{\hat{z}}(z) dz,$$

where VaR_{β} is the Value-at-Risk as defined above.

Remember that we assumed the continuity of the distribution function $F_{\hat{z}}$. If this is not the case, for example if the random variable \hat{z} has a discrete probability distribution, the definition of CVaR has to be modified (cf. [RU02]).

[†]In some publications the concept of Conditional Value-at-Risk is called *Average Value-at-Risk*, for reasons that are well explained in [SDR09, Theorem 6.2]. You can also find notations where the subscript β is the complementary probability of our probability level.

2.3.2 Properties

A very useful property of the Conditional Value-at-Risk was proven by Rockafellar and Uryasev in [RU00]. They showed that CVaR can be written as the minimum of a convex function, which turns out to be easier to handle than the original Definition 2.3.2, involving the Value-at-Risk. We will see that this equivalent formulation enables us to incorporate the mentioned convex function into the objective function of a mean-risk minimization problem as introduced in Section 2.2.3.

Let $\beta \in (0, 1)$ be a probability level. The function $F_\beta : L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P}) \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined as

$$(\hat{z}, \alpha) \mapsto F_\beta(\hat{z}, \alpha) := \alpha + (1 - \beta)^{-1} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [z - \alpha]^+ p_z(z) dz, \quad (2.3.2)$$

where $[t]^+ := \max\{0, t\}$ for all $t \in \mathbb{R}$ and p_z is the density of random variable \hat{z} . The following theorem shows the mentioned relationship between CVaR_β and F_β .

Theorem 2.3.3 (Characterization of CVaR, cf. [RU00, Theorem 1]) Let $\beta \in (0, 1)$ be a probability level.

- (i) For fixed $\hat{z} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$, the function $F_\beta(\hat{z}, \cdot)$ as defined above is convex and continuously differentiable.
- (ii) The β -CVaR of any loss-function $\hat{z} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ can be determined by the formula

$$\text{CVaR}_\beta(\hat{z}) = \min_{\alpha \in \mathbb{R}} F_\beta(\hat{z}, \alpha).$$

- (iii) The set consisting of the values of α for which the minimum in (ii) is attained, namely

$$A_\beta(\hat{z}) := \operatorname{argmin}_{\alpha \in \mathbb{R}} F_\beta(\hat{z}, \alpha)$$

with $\hat{z} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$, is a non-empty, closed, and bounded interval, and the β -VaR of the loss is given by

$$\text{VaR}_\beta(\hat{z}) = \min A_\beta(\hat{z}).$$

- (iv) The statements in (ii) and (iii) immediately imply the relation

$$\text{CVaR}_\beta(\hat{z}) = F_\beta(\hat{z}, \text{VaR}_\beta(\hat{z}))$$

for every $\hat{z} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$.

The assumption that the distribution function F_z is continuous still holds as it does for the remainder of this thesis. This is necessary to prove part (i) of the theorem. The gain of this theorem is that we can now calculate the β -CVaR without having calculated the β -VaR first. Nonetheless, we are still able to obtain the β -VaR from (iii) if this should be necessary.

When it comes to application in the real world, we often do not know the density p_z of \hat{z} in advance. In this case, being able to work with a set of scenarios/samples would be helpful. Let $\{(z_s, p_s) \in \mathbb{R} \times [0, 1] \mid s \in \{1, \dots, S\}\}$ be such a set with $S \in \mathbb{N}$ scenarios, each of which consisting of a realization z_s of \hat{z} and an associated probability p_s such that $\sum_{s=1}^S p_s = 1$. We can now approximate the integral in (2.3.2) by a finite sum such that the approximation of $F_\beta(\hat{z}, \alpha)$ for

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some $\hat{z} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ and $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{F}_\beta &: \mathbb{R}^S \times [0, 1]^S \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \\ (z, p, \alpha) &\mapsto \tilde{F}_\beta(z, p, \alpha) := \alpha + (1 - \beta)^{-1} \sum_{s=1}^S [z_s - \alpha]^+ p_s. \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.3)$$

For fixed $(z, p) \in \mathbb{R}^S \times [0, 1]^S$, the function $\tilde{F}_\beta(z, p, \cdot)$ is still convex and piecewise linear but not differentiable any more (cf. [RU00, Page 6]). In accordance with [Theorem 2.3.3](#) (ii), we can then define the Conditional Value-at-Risk as follows.

Definition 2.3.4 (Conditional Value-at-Risk for a Set of Samples) Let $z \in \mathbb{R}^S$ be a vector of $S \in \mathbb{N}$ samples from a random variable $\hat{z} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ with associated probabilities $p \in [0, 1]^S$ such that $\sum_{s=1}^S p_s = 1$, as described above. Then the approximation of $\text{CVaR}_\beta(\hat{z})$ is denoted by $\text{CVaR}_\beta(z, p)$ and defined as

$$\text{CVaR}_\beta(z, p) := \min_{\alpha \in \mathbb{R}} \tilde{F}_\beta(z, p, \alpha),$$

where \tilde{F}_β is the function defined in (2.3.3).

Note that we use the same notation as in [Definition 2.3.2](#) with the difference that now the argument is not a random variable but a tuple of sampled values and associated probabilities.

3 A Non-Smooth Approach to Optimizing the CVaR

In this chapter we use non-smooth optimization methods in order to develop a so-called *primal-dual algorithm* that minimizes an objective function involving the Conditional Value-at-Risk. While in the first section we specify the structure of the problem, the second section is devoted to deriving its optimality conditions. In the third section we present an algorithm that computes the projection onto the so-called *bounded probability simplex*, which will be a key-task of the primal-dual algorithm described in the last section.

3.1 Problem Formulation

In this section we formulate the non-smooth optimization problem we want to solve.

Let $n, S \in \mathbb{N}$ be positive integers, $H : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ a proper, convex and lower semi-continuous function and $D \in L(\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}^S)$ a linear operator. As in [Section 2.3.1](#), $\gamma \geq 0$ is the weight of the risk measure and $\beta \in (0, 1)$ the probability level of CVaR. The vector $v \in \mathbb{R}^S$ allows for an affine transformation in the argument of CVaR and $p \in [0, 1]^S$ is a vector of probabilities such that $\sum_{s=1}^S p_s = 1$. The problem we address in this chapter can then be expressed as

$$\min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} H(x) + \gamma \text{CVaR}_\beta(Dx + v, p) \quad (3.1.1a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } Bx \leq b, \quad (3.1.1b)$$

where the $m \in \mathbb{N}$ constraints are given by a linear operator $B \in L(\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}^m)$ and a vector $b \in \mathbb{R}^m$. Note that we use [Definition 2.3.4](#) to describe the Conditional Value-at-Risk, i.e. we implicitly require the argument of CVaR to be a vector of samples from some random variable, together with the associated probabilities.

The following section requires that we incorporate the linear constraints into the objective function. This can be done by defining the set $\mathcal{U}_b := \{u \in \mathbb{R}^m \mid u \leq b\}$ and introducing the following functions, where $\delta_{\mathcal{U}_b}$ denotes the indicator function* of \mathcal{U}_b :

$$K : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m, \quad x \mapsto Kx := (Dx, Bx)^\top, \quad (3.1.2)$$

$$G_v : \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}, \quad (z, u) \mapsto G_v(z, u) := \gamma \text{CVaR}_\beta(z + v, p) + \delta_{\mathcal{U}_b}(u). \quad (3.1.3)$$

With this, problem [\(3.1.1\)](#) is equivalent to

$$\min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} H(x) + G_v(Kx). \quad (3.1.4)$$

3.2 Optimality Conditions

In this section we derive the optimality conditions of problem [\(3.1.4\)](#). These conditions require some properties of the involved functions CVaR_β and G_v , which we present in the following lemmas.

* Recall that, for any dimension $d \in \mathbb{N}$ and any subset $\mathcal{M} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, the indicator function $\delta_{\mathcal{M}} : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \{0, \infty\}$ is defined as

$$\lambda \mapsto \delta_{\mathcal{M}}(\lambda) := \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \lambda \in \mathcal{M}, \\ \infty, & \text{if } \lambda \notin \mathcal{M}. \end{cases}$$

Lemma 3.2.1 (Equivalent Formulation of CVaR) Let $S \in \mathbb{N}$, $z \in \mathbb{R}^S$, $p \in [0, 1]^S$ such that $\sum_{s=1}^S p_s = 1$ and $\beta \in (0, 1)$. If CVaR_β is defined as in Definition 2.3.4, it satisfies

$$\text{CVaR}_\beta(z, p) = \sup_{\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^S} (\lambda^\top z - \delta_{\mathcal{A}_p}(\lambda)),$$

where $\mathcal{A}_p := \{ \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^S \mid \lambda^\top \mathbf{1} = 1 \text{ and } 0 \leq \lambda_s \leq (1 - \beta)^{-1} p_s \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, S\} \}$ and $\mathbf{1} \in \mathbb{R}^S$ denotes the vector of all ones.

Proof: First we employ Definition 2.3.4 to get

$$\text{CVaR}_\beta(z, p) = \min_{\alpha \in \mathbb{R}} \left(\alpha + (1 - \beta)^{-1} \sum_{s=1}^S [z_s - \alpha]^+ p_s \right). \quad (3.2.1)$$

The use of the function $[\cdot]^+$ can be avoided by introducing new variables $w_s \in \mathbb{R}$ for every $s \in \{1, \dots, S\}$. The minimization on the right-hand side is then equivalent to

$$\min_{\alpha \in \mathbb{R}, w \in \mathbb{R}^S} \alpha + (1 - \beta)^{-1} \sum_{s=1}^S w_s p_s \quad (3.2.2a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \alpha + w_s \geq z_s \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, S\}, \quad (3.2.2b)$$

$$w_s \geq 0 \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, S\}. \quad (3.2.2c)$$

Since this is a linear optimization problem, it is equivalent to its dual problem due to strong duality (cf. [BT97, Theorem 4.4]). Following Chapter 4.2 in [BT97], the dual can be written as

$$\max_{\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^S} \sum_{s=1}^S \lambda_s z_s \quad (3.2.3a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } 0 \leq \lambda_s \leq (1 - \beta)^{-1} p_s \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, S\}, \quad (3.2.3b)$$

$$\sum_{s=1}^S \lambda_s = 1. \quad (3.2.3c)$$

Now, the definitions of \mathcal{A}_p and the indicator function $\delta_{\mathcal{A}_p}$ immediately imply

$$\text{CVaR}_\beta(z, p) = \sup_{\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^S} (\lambda^\top z - \delta_{\mathcal{A}_p}(\lambda)). \quad (3.2.4)$$

□

With this representation of CVaR_β we can now show some essential properties of G_v .

Lemma 3.2.2 (Properties of G_v) Let $v \in \mathbb{R}^S$ and $G_v : \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be defined as in Section 3.1. Then, G_v is

- (i) proper,
- (ii) convex,
- (iii) and lower semi-continuous.

Proof: Let $b \in \mathbb{R}^m$ and $\varphi : \mathbb{R}^S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^S$ be defined as $z \mapsto \varphi(z) := (z + v, p)$. We can then write $G_v(z, u) = \gamma(\text{CVaR}_\beta \circ \varphi)(z) + \delta_{\mathcal{V}_b}(u)$ for all $z \in \mathbb{R}^S$ and $u \in \mathbb{R}^m$.

(i) The indicator function $\delta_{\mathcal{U}_b}$ is proper since $\mathcal{U}_b = \{u \in \mathbb{R}^m \mid u \leq b\}$ is not empty. Furthermore, we can use [Lemma 3.2.1](#) to show that $\text{CVaR}_{\beta^\circ} \varphi$ is real-valued:

- The assumptions $\sum_{s=1}^S p_s = 1$ and $\beta \in (0, 1)$ immediately imply that $p \in \mathcal{A}_p$ and therefore $\mathcal{A}_p \neq \emptyset$.
- The set \mathcal{A}_p is bounded, i.e. there exists a radius $r > 0$ such that $\mathcal{A}_p \subset \{z \in \mathbb{R}^S \mid \|z\|_2 \leq r\}$, where $\|\cdot\|_2$ is the Euclidean norm on \mathbb{R}^S . Thus we have $\sup_{\lambda \in \mathcal{A}_p} \lambda^\top z < \infty$ and therefore $\sup_{\lambda \in \mathcal{A}_p} \lambda^\top (z + v) < \infty$ for all $z \in \mathbb{R}^S$.

These two observations imply that $(\text{CVaR}_{\beta^\circ} \varphi)(z) \in \mathbb{R}$ for all $z \in \mathbb{R}^S$. Together with the properness of $\delta_{\mathcal{U}_b}$ we conclude that G_v is proper.

(ii) The convexity of $\delta_{\mathcal{U}_b}$ follows immediately from the fact that \mathcal{U}_b is a convex set for every $b \in \mathbb{R}^m$. To show convexity of $\text{CVaR}_{\beta^\circ} \varphi$, we first define for every $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^S$ the function

$$F_\lambda : \mathbb{R}^S \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{-\infty\}, \quad z \mapsto F_\lambda(z) := \lambda^\top (z + v) - \delta_{\mathcal{A}_p}(\lambda). \quad (3.2.5)$$

It can easily be seen that F_λ is convex for every $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^S$ and therefore

$$\text{CVaR}_{\beta^\circ} \varphi = \sup_{\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^S} F_\lambda \quad (3.2.6)$$

is convex as well (cf. [Lemma 2.1.1](#) (iv)). Since $\gamma \geq 0$ and $\text{CVaR}_{\beta^\circ} \varphi$ and $\delta_{\mathcal{U}_b}$ depend on different variables, it follows from [Lemma 2.1.1](#) (i) that G_v is a convex function.

(iii) The lower semi-continuity of G_v can be proved in three steps:

- \mathcal{U}_b is closed and convex for every $b \in \mathbb{R}^m$, which implies the lower semi-continuity of $\delta_{\mathcal{U}_b}$ (cf. [[Cla17](#), Lemma 2.4 (ii)]).
- $\text{CVaR}_{\beta^\circ} \varphi$ is lower semi-continuous as the point-wise supremum of lower semi-continuous functionals (cf. (3.2.5) and [[Cla17](#), Lemma 2.2 (v)]). Here we have used the fact that, in finite-dimensional spaces, weak lower semi-continuity is equivalent to lower semi-continuity.
- Together with [[Cla17](#), Lemma 2.2 (i)-(ii)] we have that G_v is lower semi-continuous.

□

We can now apply [Theorem 2.1.3](#) and deduce that $x^* \in \text{dom}(H + G_v \circ K)$ is a global minimizer in (3.1.4) if and only if

$$0 \in \partial(H + G_v \circ K)(x^*). \quad (3.2.7)$$

According to [Lemma 3.2.2](#) (ii), G_v is convex and [Lemma 2.1.1](#) (iii) implies that $G_v \circ K$ is convex as well, since K is a linear function. Therefore, we can apply the sum rule ([Theorem 2.1.4](#)) in (3.2.7) to get the condition

$$0 \in \partial H(x^*) + \partial(G_v \circ K)(x^*), \quad (3.2.8)$$

under the assumption that there exists an $x_0 \in \text{dom}(H)^\circ \cap \text{dom}(G_v \circ K)$. The convexity of G_v also allows us to use the chain rule ([Theorem 2.1.5](#)) and rewrite (3.2.8) as

$$0 \in \partial H(x^*) + K^* \partial G_v(Kx^*), \quad (3.2.9)$$

where K^* is the adjoint operator of K , which is equal to K^\top due to the finite dimension. If this

condition is satisfied, there must be a $y^* \in \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m$ such that

$$\begin{cases} -K^*y^* \in \partial H(x^*), \\ y^* \in \partial G_v(Kx^*). \end{cases} \quad (3.2.10)$$

Due to [Lemma 3.2.2](#), all assumptions of [Lemma 2.1.10](#) are satisfied and we can apply it to the second condition in (3.2.10) to get the equivalent formulation

$$\begin{cases} -K^*y^* \in \partial H(x^*), \\ Kx^* \in \partial G_v^*(y^*), \end{cases} \quad (3.2.11)$$

where G_v^* is the Fenchel conjugate of G_v (cf. [Definition 2.1.6](#)).

For the next step it is necessary that H and G_v^* are proper, convex, and lower semi-continuous. H satisfies these conditions by definition and G_v^* is the Fenchel conjugate of a proper function (cf. [Lemma 3.2.2 \(i\)](#)) and as such convex and lower semi-continuous (cf. [[Cla17](#), Page 42]). Furthermore, [Lemma 3.2.2 \(i\)-\(iii\)](#) imply that G^* is bounded from below by an affine functional and thus proper (cf. [[Cla17](#), Page 42]). This justifies the application of [Lemma 2.1.12](#) to the optimality condition (3.2.11), yielding

$$\begin{cases} x^* = \text{prox}_{\tau H}(x^* - \tau K^*y^*), \\ y^* = \text{prox}_{\sigma G_v^*}(y^* + \sigma Kx^*), \end{cases} \quad (3.2.12)$$

with $\tau, \sigma > 0$.

The following corollary gives an explicit description of the proximal point mapping of σG_v^* .

Corollary 3.2.3 (Proximal Point Mapping of σG_v^*) Let $\sigma > 0$, $v \in \mathbb{R}^S$ and the function $G_v : \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \bar{\mathbb{R}}$ be defined as in [Section 3.1](#). Then, the proximal point mapping $\text{prox}_{\sigma G_v^*} : \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m$ is given by

$$(y_1, y_2) \mapsto \text{prox}_{\sigma G_v^*}(y_1, y_2) := \begin{pmatrix} \gamma \text{proj}_{\mathcal{A}_p}(\gamma^{-1}y_1 + \sigma \gamma^{-1}v) \\ y_2 - \sigma \min\{\sigma^{-1}y_2, b\} \end{pmatrix},$$

where $\text{proj}_{\mathcal{A}_p}$ denotes the Euclidean projection onto the set \mathcal{A}_p (cf. equation (3.2.18)).

Proof: Let $\varphi : \mathbb{R}^S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m$ be defined as $z \mapsto \varphi(z) := (z + v, p)$. First, we have a closer look at the Fenchel conjugate G_v^* and use [Definition 2.1.6](#) to find that for every $(w, z) \in \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m =: X$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} G_v^*(w, z) &= \sup_{(w', z') \in \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m} (\langle (w, z), (w', z') \rangle_X - G_v(w, z)) \\ &\stackrel{(3.1.3)}{=} \sup_{(w', z') \in \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m} (\langle (w, z), (w', z') \rangle_X - \gamma (\text{CVaR}_{\beta^\circ} \varphi)(w) - \delta_{\mathcal{U}_b}(z)) \\ &= \sup_{w' \in \mathbb{R}^S} (\langle w, w' \rangle_{\mathbb{R}^S} - \gamma (\text{CVaR}_{\beta^\circ} \varphi)(w)) + \sup_{z' \in \mathbb{R}^m} (\langle z, z' \rangle_{\mathbb{R}^m} - \delta_{\mathcal{U}_b}(z)) \\ &= (\gamma \text{CVaR}_{\beta^\circ} \varphi)^*(w) + \delta_{\mathcal{U}_b}^*(z). \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.13)$$

According to Lemma 2.1.13 (iii), we can then split the proximal point mapping to get

$$\text{prox}_{\sigma G_v^*}(y_1, y_2) = \begin{pmatrix} \text{prox}_{\sigma(\gamma \text{CVaR}_{\beta^\circ \varphi})^*}(y_1) \\ \text{prox}_{\sigma \delta_{\mathcal{U}_b}^*}(y_2) \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.2.14)$$

for every tuple $(y_1, y_2) \in \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m$. We now want to eliminate φ from this equation and therefore rearrange the first component as

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{prox}_{\sigma(\gamma \text{CVaR}_{\beta^\circ \varphi})^*}(y_1) \\ & \stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.1.13 (ii)}}{=} y_1 - \sigma \text{prox}_{\sigma^{-1} \gamma \text{CVaR}_{\beta^\circ \varphi}}(\sigma^{-1} y_1) \\ & \stackrel{\text{Lemma 2.1.13 (i)}}{=} y_1 - \sigma \left(\text{prox}_{\sigma^{-1} \gamma \text{CVaR}_{\beta}}(\sigma^{-1} y_1 + v) - v \right). \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.15)$$

According to Lemma 3.2.1 and Definition 2.1.6, CVaR_{β} is the Fenchel conjugate of the indicator function $\delta_{\mathcal{A}_p}$, i.e. $\text{CVaR}_{\beta} = \delta_{\mathcal{A}_p}^*$. Since \mathcal{A}_p is convex and closed, $\delta_{\mathcal{A}_p}$ is convex and weakly lower semi-continuous (cf. [Cla17, Lemma 2.4 (ii)]). Weak lower semi-continuity implies lower semi-continuity and therefore the assumptions of the Fenchel-Moreau-Rockafellar theorem (cf. Theorem 2.1.7) are satisfied. Thus we can identify $\delta_{\mathcal{A}_p}$ with its biconjugate to get

$$\text{CVaR}_{\beta}^* = \delta_{\mathcal{A}_p}^{**} = \delta_{\mathcal{A}_p}. \quad (3.2.16)$$

With this and Lemma 2.1.13 (i), equation (3.2.15) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{prox}_{\sigma(\gamma \text{CVaR}_{\beta^\circ \varphi})^*}(y_1) \\ & = y_1 - \sigma \left(\sigma^{-1} y_1 + v - \sigma^{-1} \gamma \text{prox}_{\sigma \gamma^{-1} \text{CVaR}_{\beta}^*}(\gamma^{-1} y_1 + \sigma \gamma^{-1} v) - v \right) \\ & = \gamma \text{prox}_{\delta_{\mathcal{A}_p}}(\gamma^{-1} y_1 + \sigma \gamma^{-1} v), \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.17)$$

where we used for the last equality that $t \delta_{\mathcal{A}_p} = \delta_{\mathcal{A}_p}$ for all $t > 0$. If we consider the definition of the proximal point mapping (cf. Definition 2.1.11), we can easily see that, for any $\tilde{y}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^S$, $\text{prox}_{\delta_{\mathcal{A}_p}}(\tilde{y}_1)$ is in fact the Euclidean projection of \tilde{y}_1 onto the set \mathcal{A}_p , i.e.

$$\text{prox}_{\delta_{\mathcal{A}_p}}(\tilde{y}_1) = \underset{z \in \mathcal{A}_p}{\text{argmin}} \frac{1}{2} \|z - \tilde{y}_1\|_2^2 =: \text{proj}_{\mathcal{A}_p}(\tilde{y}_1). \quad (3.2.18)$$

Therefore, (3.2.17) is equivalent to

$$\text{prox}_{\sigma(\gamma \text{CVaR}_{\beta^\circ \varphi})^*}(y_1) = \gamma \text{proj}_{\mathcal{A}_p}(\gamma^{-1} y_1 + \sigma \gamma^{-1} v). \quad (3.2.19)$$

We now attend to the second component of equation (3.2.14). It follows from Lemma 2.1.13 (ii) that

$$\begin{aligned} \text{prox}_{\sigma \delta_{\mathcal{U}_b}^*}(y_2) & = y_2 - \sigma \text{prox}_{\sigma^{-1} \delta_{\mathcal{U}_b}}(\sigma^{-1} y_2) \\ & = y_2 - \sigma \text{prox}_{\delta_{\mathcal{U}_b}}(\sigma^{-1} y_2). \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.20)$$

From equation (3.2.18) (with the set \mathcal{U}_b instead of \mathcal{A}_p) we know that $\text{prox}_{\delta_{\mathcal{U}_b}} = \text{proj}_{\mathcal{U}_b}$ and due to the specific structure of \mathcal{U}_b , i.e. $\mathcal{U}_b = \{z \in \mathbb{R}^m \mid z \leq b\}$, it follows from Section 4.1.6

in [Ceg13] that

$$\text{prox}_{\delta_{\mathcal{L}_b}}(z) = \text{proj}_{\mathcal{L}_b}(z) = \min\{z, b\} \quad (3.2.21)$$

for every $z \in \mathbb{R}^m$, where the minimum on the right hand side is meant componentwise. Therefore, (3.2.20) is equivalent to

$$\text{prox}_{\sigma\delta_{\mathcal{L}_b}}(y_2) = y_2 - \sigma \min\{\sigma^{-1}y_2, b\}. \quad (3.2.22)$$

Combining equations (3.2.14), (3.2.19) and (3.2.22) concludes the proof. \square

Now that we know how to write the second equation of (3.2.12) explicitly, we still need to consider the first. So far we have only required $H : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ to be proper, convex and lower semi-continuous. From now on we assume that H is linear, i.e. there is a vector $h \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $H(x) = h^\top x$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$. This allows us to use the following explicit formulation of the corresponding proximal point mapping. For every $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ we have

$$\text{prox}_{\tau H}(x) \stackrel{\text{Definition 2.1.11}}{=} \underset{x' \in \mathbb{R}^n}{\text{argmin}} \left(\frac{1}{2} \|x' - x\|_2^2 + \tau h^\top x' \right) = x - \tau h, \quad (3.2.23)$$

where the last equality can be obtained by setting the first derivative of $\frac{1}{2} \|x' - x\|_2^2 + \tau h^\top x'$ (with respect to x') to zero and solving for x' . Note that the optimality conditions can easily be modified if H takes another specific form, as long as its proximal point mapping has an explicit representation.

If we use (3.2.23) and Corollary 3.2.3 together with the definition of K (cf. (3.1.2)), optimality condition (3.2.12) becomes

$$\begin{cases} x^* = x^* - \tau(K^*(y_1^*, y_2^*) + h), \\ y_1^* = \gamma \text{proj}_{\mathcal{A}_p}(\gamma^{-1}y_1^* + \sigma\gamma^{-1}Dx^* + \sigma\gamma^{-1}v), \\ y_2^* = y_2^* + \sigma Bx^* - \sigma \min\{\sigma^{-1}y_2^* + Bx^*, b\}. \end{cases} \quad (3.2.24)$$

Apparently, the Euclidean projection onto \mathcal{A}_p is an important part of these optimality conditions. The question how this projection can be calculated efficiently is addressed in the following section.

3.3 Projection onto the Bounded Probability Simplex

In this section we develop an efficient algorithm for computing the Euclidean projection of a point $y = (y_1, \dots, y_n)^\top \in \mathbb{R}^n$ onto the bounded probability simplex, which is defined as the set

$$\mathcal{A}_p := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid x^\top \mathbf{1} = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad 0 \leq x \leq p\mathbf{1}\}, \quad (3.3.1)$$

where $\mathbf{1} := (1, \dots, 1)^\top \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $p \geq \frac{1}{n}$ is a real number. Note that we now consider the same upper bound p for all components of x in contrast to the definition of \mathcal{A}_p in Lemma 3.2.1. This implies in the framework of the CVaR that $p = (1 - \beta)^{-1}p_s$ for all $s \in \{1, \dots, S\}$, i.e. all scenarios are equally likely. The assumption $p \geq \frac{1}{n}$ guarantees that \mathcal{A}_p is not empty and is needed for the proof. It does not impose any restrictions in the CVaR-framework since it is satisfied automatically for equally likely scenarios (together with $\beta \geq 0$).

Several solutions have been described for similar problems. For example, John Duchi et al. developed an algorithm to compute the projection onto the *positive simplex* (cf. [Duc+08]), i.e. they considered a set like \mathcal{A}_p but with an arbitrary value on the right-hand side of the equation in (3.3.1) and no upper bound on x . The key idea of their proof is sorting the elements of the point

being projected in a descending order and finding the last index that satisfies a certain condition. Weiran Wang and Miguel Á. Carreira-Perpiñán slightly changed this problem and used the so called *probability simplex* instead (cf. [WC13]), which means that the condition $x^\top \mathbf{1} = 1$ has to be satisfied for all x in the set (i.e. the right-hand side of the equation is not arbitrary anymore). They proposed a proof that uses the KKT conditions and also the sorting as in the previously mentioned paper. A similar approach was used by Nelson Maculan and Geraldo Galdino de Paula Jr. (cf. [MP89]).

All aforementioned authors did not consider the possibility of an upper bound on the elements of the respective set like $x \leq p\mathbf{1}$ in (3.3.1). Yunmei Chen and Xiaojing Ye used tools from the field of convex analysis like the proximal point mapping and the Fenchel conjugate to construct an algorithm where this upper bound is equal to 1 (cf. [CY11]).

The algorithm presented in the following sections is based on the ideas in [WC13] and modified such that there is an upper bound on x (cf. (3.3.1)). This upper bound can be any real, positive number. The resulting optimization problem can be described as follows:

$$\min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} \frac{1}{2} \|x - y\|_2^2 \quad (3.3.2a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } x^\top \mathbf{1} = 1, \quad (3.3.2b)$$

$$0 \leq x \leq p\mathbf{1}. \quad (3.3.2c)$$

As in [WC13], this is a quadratic program with a strictly convex objective function. The unique solution will be denoted by $x^* = (x_1^*, \dots, x_n^*)^\top \in \mathbb{R}^n$.

3.3.1 Optimality Conditions

To derive the optimality conditions for the above problem, we apply the KKT conditions (cf. [NW06, Theorem 12.1]). The Lagrangian of the problem is

$$\mathcal{L}(x, \lambda, \nu, \mu) := \frac{1}{2} \|x - y\|_2^2 - \lambda (x^\top \mathbf{1} - 1) - \nu^\top x + \mu^\top (x - p\mathbf{1}), \quad (3.3.3)$$

where $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\nu, \mu \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are the Lagrange multipliers. The following KKT conditions hold for the optimal solution x^* :

$$\nabla_x \mathcal{L}(x^*, \lambda^*, \nu^*, \mu^*) = x^* - y - \lambda^* \mathbf{1} - \nu^* + \mu^* = 0, \quad (3.3.4)$$

$$x^{*\top} \mathbf{1} - 1 = 0, \quad (3.3.5)$$

$$x_i^* \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \quad (3.3.6)$$

$$p - x_i^* \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \quad (3.3.7)$$

$$\nu_i^* \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \quad (3.3.8)$$

$$\mu_i^* \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \quad (3.3.9)$$

$$x_i^* \nu_i^* = 0 \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \quad (3.3.10)$$

$$\mu_i^* (x_i^* - p) = 0 \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}. \quad (3.3.11)$$

Now we use the complementarity conditions (3.3.10) and (3.3.11) to derive an explicit description of the optimal point x^* . Let $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. We distinguish the following cases:

- if $x_i^* > 0$ then $\nu_i^* = 0$;
- if $x_i^* < p$ then $\mu_i^* = 0$; it follows from (3.3.4) that

$$p > x_i^* = y_i + \lambda^* > 0; \quad (3.3.12)$$

- if $x_i^* = p$ then $\mu_i^* \geq 0$; it follows from (3.3.4) that

$$y_i + \lambda^* \geq x_i^* = y_i + \lambda^* - \mu_i^* = p > 0; \quad (3.3.13)$$

- if $x_i^* = 0$ then $v_i^* \geq 0$; since $p > 0$ we have $x_i^* < p$ and therefore $\mu_i^* = 0$; it follows from (3.3.4) that

$$y_i + \lambda^* = -v_i^* \leq 0. \quad (3.3.14)$$

It can easily be shown that the following x^* satisfies the KKT conditions in all of the above cases:

$$x_i^* = \max \{ \min \{ y_i + \lambda^*, p \}, 0 \}. \quad (3.3.15)$$

Since we do not know the Lagrangian multiplier λ^* in advance, we need to develop an algorithm that is able to compute it.

3.3.2 Algorithm

The following algorithm finds the optimal solution x^* to the problem (3.3.2). An implementation in MATLAB can be found in the [Appendix C.1](#) as [MATLAB-Code C.1.1](#).

Algorithm 3.1 (Euclidean projection onto the bounded probability simplex)

Input: $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $p \geq \frac{1}{n}$

1 Sort y into u : $u_1 \geq u_2 \geq \dots \geq u_n$, define $u_0 := u_1 + p$.

2 Compute $\tau = \max \left\{ 0 \leq j \leq n \mid jp + \sum_{i=j+1}^n \max\{0, u_i + p - u_j\} \leq 1 \right\}$.

3 **if** $\tau p + \sum_{i=\tau+1}^n \max\{0, u_i + p - u_\tau\} = 1$ **then**

4 Define $\lambda^* := p - u_\tau$.

5 **else**

6 Compute $p = \max \left\{ \tau < j \leq n \mid u_j + \frac{1}{j-\tau} (1 - \tau p - \sum_{i=\tau+1}^j u_i) > 0 \right\}$.

7 Define $\lambda^* := \frac{1}{p-\tau} (1 - \tau p - \sum_{i=\tau+1}^p u_i)$.

8 **end**

Output: $x^* \in \mathbb{R}^n$ s.t. $x_i^* = \max \{ \min \{ y_i + \lambda^*, p \}, 0 \}$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$

The algorithm has the following geometric interpretation: Place the values y_1, \dots, y_n as points on the abscissa. Then the optimal solution is given by a shift of these points such that the ones to the right of the ordinate sum up to 1, and whenever a point would be greater than p , it is set to p .

In the [Appendix A](#) we present a way how the computation of τ in [Line 2](#) can be implemented efficiently.

3.3.3 Proof

The proof of correctness of [Algorithm 3.1](#) is based on [[WC13](#), Chapter 3] and extended such that it is applicable to our modified assumptions. Without loss of generality we assume that the

components of y are sorted and x^* uses the same ordering, i.e.

$$y_1 \geq \dots \geq y_n, \quad (3.3.16)$$

$$\text{and } x_1^* \geq \dots \geq x_n^*. \quad (3.3.17)$$

Let furthermore $p \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ be the greatest index with $x_p^* > 0$ and $\tau \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ the greatest index with $y_\tau + \lambda^* \geq p$, where λ^* is the Lagrange multiplier of the optimal solution described in Section 3.3.1, i.e.

$$x_p^* > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad x_i^* = 0 \quad \forall i \in \{p+1, \dots, n\}, \quad (3.3.18)$$

$$y_\tau + \lambda^* \geq p \quad \text{and} \quad y_i + \lambda^* < p \quad \forall i \in \{\tau+1, \dots, n\}. \quad (3.3.19)$$

It is possible that there is no $\tau \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ with $y_\tau + \lambda^* \geq p$ at all. In this case we define $\tau := 0$. If we disregard the case where $y = (0, \dots, 0)^\top$, which has the obvious solution $x^* = (0, \dots, 0)$, there must be a $p \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ as defined above.

The KKT condition (3.3.5) implies

$$1 = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^* = \sum_{i=1}^p x_i^*, \quad (3.3.20)$$

and with (3.3.12) and (3.3.13) we get

$$1 = \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ x_i^* = p}}^p p + \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ x_i^* < p}}^p (y_i + \lambda^*) \quad (3.3.21)$$

$$= \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ y_i + \lambda^* \geq p}}^p p + \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ y_i + \lambda^* < p}}^p (y_i + \lambda^*) \quad (3.3.22)$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^{\min\{p, \tau\}} p + \sum_{i=\min\{p, \tau\}+1}^p (y_i + \lambda^*) \quad (3.3.23)$$

$$= \tau p + \sum_{i=\tau+1}^p (y_i + \lambda^*). \quad (3.3.24)$$

The last equation holds since $\tau \leq p$. Otherwise, there would be a $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that $p < j \leq \tau$, which implies $x_j^* = 0$. The choice of τ then implies $p \leq y_j + \lambda^*$ and together with (3.3.14) we have $p \leq y_j + \lambda^* \leq 0$. This leads to a contradiction to the choice of p .

Since we do not know the value of λ^* , we need to calculate τ . If we eliminate p from the sum in equation (3.3.24), we get

$$\tau p + \sum_{i=\tau+1}^n \max\{0, y_i + \lambda^*\} = 1. \quad (3.3.25)$$

This is true since for all $i \in \{p+1, \dots, n\}$ we have $x_i^* = 0$ (cf. (3.3.18)), which implies $y_i + \lambda^* \leq 0$ (cf. (3.3.14)).

To motivate the next idea, we recall the geometric interpretation at the end of Section 3.3.2. We assume that all points are non-positive. We start shifting them to the right and whenever a point reaches p , it will not be shifted any further. Obviously, there must be a last point that reaches p . All of the following points (i.e. smaller values) can still be shifted to the right but will never reach p . We will see that the following idea even makes sense if the assumption of all points being non-positive does not hold.

The previously mentioned shift is determined by the optimal Lagrange multiplier λ^* . We know from (3.3.19) that $p - y_\tau \leq \lambda^*$ and $\lambda^* < p - y_i$ for all $i \in \{\tau+1, \dots, n\}$. If we take the left-hand side

of (3.3.25), replace τ by any $j \in \{0, \dots, n\}$ and λ^* by $p - y_j$, we get the sequence

$$(z_j)_{j \in \{0, \dots, n\}} := \left(jp + \sum_{i=j+1}^n \max\{0, y_i + p - y_j\} \right)_{j \in \{0, \dots, n\}}, \quad (3.3.26)$$

where $y_0 := y_1 + p$ guarantees $y_i + p - y_0 \leq 0$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. In the framework of the geometric interpretation, the latter inequality is equivalent to the assumption of all points being non-positive. The sequence $(z_j)_{j \in \{0, \dots, n\}}$ is non-decreasing because for every $j \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} z_{j+1} &= jp + \sum_{i=j+1}^n \max\{0, y_i + p - y_{j+1}\} + \underbrace{p - \max\{0, y_{j+1} + p - y_{j+1}\}}_{=0} \\ &\stackrel{(3.3.16)}{\geq} jp + \sum_{i=j+1}^n \max\{0, y_i + p - y_j\} \\ &= z_j. \end{aligned} \quad (3.3.27)$$

Note that this property is the justification for using [Algorithm A.1](#) to find τ . The assumption $p \geq \frac{1}{n}$ (cf. input of [Algorithm 3.1](#)) implies $z_n \geq 1$, and since $z_0 = 0$, there is a maximal $j \in \{0, \dots, n\}$ satisfying $z_j \leq 1$. This maximal index turns out to be the index of the mentioned *last point that reaches p*, i.e.

$$\tau = \max \{ 0 \leq j \leq n \mid z_j \leq 1 \} \quad (3.3.28)$$

as in [Line 2](#) of [Algorithm 3.1](#), where $\tau = 0$ means that none of the points *reaches p*.

With this, we are able to calculate λ^* . If $z_\tau = 1$, equation (3.3.25) is already satisfied and the algorithm terminates with

$$\lambda^* = p - y_\tau. \quad (3.3.29)$$

Otherwise, we have $p - y_\tau < \lambda^* < p - y_{\tau+1}$. Taking p into account again, we get $\tau \neq p$ (otherwise (3.3.24) yields $\tau p = 1$ in contradiction to $z_\tau < 1$). Together with $\tau \leq p$ we have $\tau < p$. This allows us to rearrange (3.3.24) such that

$$\lambda^* = \frac{1}{p - \tau} \left(1 - \tau p - \sum_{i=\tau+1}^p y_i \right). \quad (3.3.30)$$

The last step is to prove that

$$p = \max \left\{ \tau < j \leq n \mid y_j + \frac{1}{j - \tau} \left(1 - \tau p - \sum_{i=\tau+1}^j y_i \right) > 0 \right\}. \quad (3.3.31)$$

Let $j \in \{\tau + 1, \dots, n\}$. We consider three different cases:

- if $j = p$:

$$y_p + \frac{1}{p - \tau} \left(1 - \tau p - \sum_{i=\tau+1}^p y_i \right) \stackrel{(3.3.30)}{=} y_p + \lambda^* \stackrel{(3.3.13)}{>} 0; \quad (3.3.32)$$

- if $\tau < j < p$:

$$y_j + \frac{1}{j - \tau} \left(1 - \tau p - \sum_{i=\tau+1}^j y_i \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{1}{j-\tau} \left((j-\tau)y_j + 1 - \tau p - \underbrace{\sum_{i=\tau+1}^p y_i + \sum_{i=j+1}^p y_i}_{\stackrel{(3.3.30)}{=} (p-\tau)\lambda^*} \right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{j-\tau} \left((j-\tau)(y_j + \lambda^*) + \sum_{i=j+1}^p (y_i + \lambda^*) \right) \stackrel{(3.3.13)}{>} 0; \tag{3.3.33}
 \end{aligned}$$

• if $j > p$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &y_j + \frac{1}{j-\tau} \left(1 - \tau p - \sum_{i=\tau+1}^j y_i \right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{j-\tau} \left((j-\tau)y_j + 1 - \tau p - \underbrace{\sum_{i=\tau+1}^p y_i - \sum_{i=p+1}^j y_i}_{\stackrel{(3.3.30)}{=} (p-\tau)\lambda^*} \right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{j-\tau} \left(\underbrace{(p-\tau)(y_j + \lambda^*)}_{\stackrel{(3.3.14)}{\leq} 0} + \sum_{i=p+1}^j \underbrace{(y_j - y_i)}_{\stackrel{(3.3.16)}{\leq} 0} \right) \leq 0. \tag{3.3.34}
 \end{aligned}$$

This justifies the choice of p and guarantees that we find the optimal λ^* in any possible case. Together with (3.3.15) we get the optimal solution, which concludes the proof. \square

3.4 Primal-Dual Algorithm

In this section we use the optimality conditions (3.2.24) from section Section 3.2 to develop a primal-dual algorithm that solves problem (3.1.4). We also elaborate under which conditions the convergence of this algorithm can be proven.

Let us first recall the structure of original problem (cf. (3.1.1)):

$$\min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} H(x) + \gamma \text{CVaR}_\beta(Dx + v, p) \tag{3.4.1a}$$

$$\text{s.t. } Bx \leq b, \tag{3.4.1b}$$

where all definitions are adopted from Section 3.1. The assumption from Section 3.3 that all scenarios are equally likely implies that $p_s = S^{-1}$ for all $s \in \{1, \dots, S\}$. Therefore, the set $\mathcal{A}_p = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^S \mid \lambda^\top \mathbf{1} = 1 \text{ and } 0 \leq \lambda \leq (S(1-\beta))^{-1}\}$ solely depends on S and β .

We now adopt the primal-dual extragradient method introduced by Antonin Chambolle and Thomas Pock in [CP11]. It was developed to solve problems of the form (3.1.4) and can therefore be employed to solve optimality condition (3.2.24). As a stopping criterion, we check in every step $k \in \mathbb{N}$ if the current variables x^k and y^k already satisfy the optimality conditions *well enough*, i.e. if

$$\left\| \tau (K^*(y_1^k, y_2^k) + h) \right\|_2 < \varepsilon, \tag{3.4.2a}$$

$$\left\| y_1^k - \gamma \text{proj}_{\mathcal{A}_p} (\gamma^{-1} y_1^k + \sigma \gamma^{-1} D x^k + \sigma \gamma^{-1} v) \right\|_2 < \varepsilon, \tag{3.4.2b}$$

$$\text{and } \left\| -\sigma B x^k + \sigma \min \{ \sigma^{-1} y_2^k + B x^k, b \} \right\|_2 < \varepsilon, \tag{3.4.2c}$$

for $\varepsilon > 0$ sufficiently small.

Let $x^0 \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $y^0 := (y_1^0, y_2^0) \in \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m$ denote the starting vectors. [Algorithm 3.2](#) solves the original problem (3.1.1) and can be implemented in MATLAB as shown in the [Appendix C.1](#) (cf. [MATLAB-Code C.1.4](#)).

The convergence of this algorithm can be shown with the help of Theorem 7.8 in [Cla17]. It says that the generated sequence $\{(x^k, y^k)\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ converges weakly in $\mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m$ to a pair (x^*, y^*) satisfying the optimality conditions (3.2.24) if the following assumptions are satisfied:

- $\tau\sigma\|K\|^2 < 1$, where $\|\cdot\| : L(\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ is the operator norm defined by

$$M \mapsto \|M\| := \|M\|_{L(\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m)} := \sup_{\|x\|_{\mathbb{R}^n} \leq 1} \|Mx\|_{\mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m} \quad (3.4.3)$$

and $\|\cdot\|_{\mathbb{R}^n}$ and $\|\cdot\|_{\mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^m}$ are the norms of the respective vector spaces;

- H and G_v are proper, convex, and lower semi-continuous. These properties were proven for G_v in [Lemma 3.2.2](#); H satisfies them by definition;
- problem (3.1.4) admits a solution $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$;
- there exists an $x_0 \in \text{dom}(H) \cap \text{dom}(G_v \circ K)$ with $Kx_0 \in (\text{dom}(G_v))^\circ$.

Since all considered vector spaces are finite-dimensional, this theorem not only proves weak but also strong convergence of [Algorithm 3.2](#). An alternative proof is given in [CP11, Theorem 1(c)].

Algorithm 3.2 (Solving the original problem)

Input: $K^*, B, D, S, b, v, h, \beta, \gamma, \tau, \sigma, x^0, y^0$ and ε as defined above

1 Initialize $k \leftarrow 0$ and define $\bar{x}^0 := x^0$.

2 **repeat**

3 $y_1^{k+1} = \gamma \text{proj}_{\mathcal{A}_p} (\gamma^{-1} y_1^k + \sigma \gamma^{-1} D \bar{x}^k + \sigma \gamma^{-1} v)$

4 $y_2^{k+1} = y_2^k + \sigma B \bar{x}^k - \sigma \min \{ \sigma^{-1} y_2^k + B \bar{x}^k, b \}$

5 $x^{k+1} = x^k - \tau (K^*(y_1^{k+1}, y_2^{k+1}) + h)$

6 $\bar{x}^{k+1} = 2x^{k+1} - x^k$

7 Update $k \leftarrow k + 1$.

8 **until** $\|\tau (K^*(y_1^k, y_2^k) + h)\|_2 < \varepsilon$ **and**

$\|y_1^k - \gamma \text{proj}_{\mathcal{A}_p} (\gamma^{-1} y_1^k + \sigma \gamma^{-1} D x^k + \sigma \gamma^{-1} v)\|_2 < \varepsilon$ **and**

$\|-\sigma B x^k + \sigma \min \{ \sigma^{-1} y_2^k + B x^k, b \}\|_2 < \varepsilon$

Output: x^k, y^k

4 Applications

This chapter presents two applications of the algorithm introduced in [Chapter 3](#). In the first section we examine a rather small portfolio optimization problem in order to verify the correctness of [Algorithm 3.2](#) and to obtain some generic results about the relationship between the choice of parameters and the algorithm's performance. The second section discusses a larger problem related to power plant operation planning and shows how the algorithm behaves if the number of variables/constraints becomes large.

4.1 Portfolio Optimization

In this section we use a simple portfolio optimization model introduced by Rockafellar and Uryasev in [[RU00](#), Chapter 3] to check if [Algorithm 3.2](#) works properly and to get an idea about how the parameters should be chosen.

4.1.1 Problem Formulation

We consider a portfolio of three financial instruments. The decision vector $x \in \mathbb{R}^3$ represents the structure of the portfolio in the sense that x_j is the position in instrument j such that

$$x_j \geq 0 \quad \forall j \in \{1, 2, 3\} \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{j=1}^3 x_j = 1. \quad (4.1.1)$$

The random vector $\hat{y} := (\hat{y}_1, \hat{y}_2, \hat{y}_3) : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ denotes the return on the respective instruments, where $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ is a probability space as in [Section 2.3.1](#). \hat{y} has a joint distribution of the individual returns and is assumed to be independent of x . Its density will be denoted by $p : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow [0, \infty)$.

The return on a portfolio x can be expressed as the sum of the individual returns, weighted with the respective proportion x_j . Since the loss is the negative of this, the loss-function is given by

$$f(x, \hat{y}) = -(x_1 \hat{y}_1 + x_2 \hat{y}_2 + x_3 \hat{y}_3) = -x^\top \hat{y} \quad (4.1.2)$$

for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^3$.

Furthermore, we impose the restriction that only portfolios with an expected return exceeding a given amount $R \in \mathbb{R}$ will be admitted. If we denote the expected value of \hat{y} by $m \in \mathbb{R}^3$, the expected loss of portfolio x is given by $\mathbb{E}[f(x, \hat{y})] = -x^\top m$. Therefore, this constraint can be written as

$$x^\top m \geq R. \quad (4.1.3)$$

Let $\beta \in (0, 1)$ be a probability level. The objective is minimizing the risk of the portfolio in terms of the Conditional Value-at-Risk, subject to the above constraints. Thus the overall problem is

$$\min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^3} \text{CVaR}_\beta(f(x, \hat{y})) \quad (4.1.4)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad (4.1.1), (4.1.3), \quad (4.1.5)$$

which can be easily written in the form of problem [\(3.1.1\)](#) by setting $h = 0$ (i.e. H is the zero function), $v = 0$ (i.e. there is no affine shift in the argument of CVaR) and $\gamma = 1$.

4.1.2 Data

The matrix B and the vector b are defined such that they represent the linear restrictions (4.1.1) and (4.1.3), where the minimum expected return is assumed to be $R = 0.011$. The matrix D is obtained by sampling the portfolio return data from a joint multivariate normal distribution. The underlying parameters are shown in Tables 4.1 and 4.2, which were adopted from [RU00]. An implementation of this portfolio optimization problem in MATLAB can be found in the Appendix C.2 as MATLAB-Code C.2.1.

Instrument	Expected Return
1	0.0101110
2	0.0043532
3	0.0137058

Table 4.1: Expected Return

Instrument	1	2	3
1	0.00324625	0.00022983	0.00420395
2	0.00022983	0.00049937	0.00019247
3	0.00420395	0.00019247	0.00764097

Table 4.2: Covariance Matrix

4.1.3 Numerical Results

Table 4.3 shows in an exemplary way how the choice of the parameters τ and σ affects the performance of the algorithm. They were both chosen from the set $\{0.1, 0.4, 0.7, 1.0\}$. However, not every combination appears in the table since the choices for which the algorithm did not converge were left out. The fifth column contains the value of $\tau\sigma\|K\|^2$, which needs to be less than 1 in order to guarantee convergence (cf. Page 24). However, the algorithm can converge even if the value is greater than or equal to 1. ΔCVaR denotes the relative difference of the optimal CVaR and the exact optimal CVaR. The latter can be found in the second column and was computed by the `linprog`-method of MATLAB, applied to the linearized model in [RU00, Chapter 3]. All calculations were carried out on a 2.6 GHz Intel i5 machine. The number of scenarios is 1000 and the tolerance parameter ε was set to 10^{-6} . All CVaR-values in the table are rounded to four decimal places and the rows are ordered by the computation time.

Apparently, the elapsed time depends roughly on the value of $\tau\sigma\|K\|^2$ such that greater values of the latter imply a shorter computation time. While this statement is exactly true for $\beta = 0.99$, there are some data that deviate from this assumption, e.g. the third and fourth row for $\beta = 0.90$. Nonetheless, we can still deduce that choosing τ and σ such that $\tau\sigma\|K\|^2$ is close to 0 is likely to slow down the algorithm significantly. However, choosing them too large can cause the algorithm to fail. Therefore, some parameter combinations are not mentioned in the table (e.g. $\tau = 0.4, \sigma = 0.7$).

The question how τ and σ should be chosen if we assume a given value of $\tau\sigma\|K\|^2$ can not be answered conclusively. For $\beta = 0.90$, the solution with $\tau = 0.1$ and $\sigma = 1.0$ takes only about 68% of the time that is needed to solve the problem with $\tau = 1.0$ and $\sigma = 0.1$. However, this relation is inverted if we consider $\beta = 0.99$.

Finally, we note that the relative difference of the CVaR found by Algorithm 3.2 and the exact CVaR found by the `linprog`-method of MATLAB lies between -0.1% and 0.1% for $\beta = 0.90$, and between -0.14% and 0.14% for $\beta = 0.99$. Whether this tolerance is sufficient or not clearly depends on the particular application. However, if these intervals are considered small enough, one can conclude that the choice of $\varepsilon = 10^{-6}$ leads to the desired accuracy.

Figures 4.1 and 4.2 give an insight into the process of approximating the optimal solution. The data was collected for $\beta = 0.90$ and $\beta = 0.99$, where τ and σ were both set to 0.4. Subfigure (a) shows the function value, i.e. the CVaR, per iteration in blue and the `linprog`-solution in red, and

β	optimal CVaR	τ	σ	$\tau\sigma\ K\ ^2$	Time (in sec)	CVaR	ΔCVaR (in %)
0.90	0.0965	0.4	0.4	2.60	12.39	0.0965	0.00
		0.1	1.0	1.62	13.07	0.0965	0.00
		0.1	0.7	1.14	13.90	0.0965	0.00
		1.0	0.1	1.62	19.16	0.0966	0.10
		0.1	0.4	0.65	21.13	0.0965	0.00
		0.7	0.1	1.14	23.10	0.0964	-0.10
		0.4	0.1	0.65	27.13	0.0964	-0.10
		0.1	0.1	0.16	47.54	0.0964	-0.10
0.99	0.1472	0.4	0.4	2.60	341.42	0.1472	0.00
		1.0	0.1	1.62	419.06	0.1474	0.14
		0.1	1.0	1.62	574.46	0.1472	0.00
		0.7	0.1	1.14	602.59	0.1470	-0.14
		0.1	0.7	1.14	690.66	0.1472	0.00
		0.4	0.1	0.65	1046.32	0.1474	0.14
		0.1	0.4	0.65	1275.63	0.1472	0.00
		0.1	0.1	0.16	3977.10	0.1470	-0.14

Table 4.3: Results of the Portfolio Optimization

subfigure (b) displays the Euclidean norm of the error, i.e. the difference of the solution vector at the current iteration and the optimal solution vector found by the `linprog`-method.

Figure 4.1: Plots for $\beta = 0.90$ and $\tau = \sigma = 0.4$

For $\beta = 0.90$, i.e. Figure 4.1, the function value after about 10,000 iterations is already pretty close to the correct solution and does not change significantly any more. However, the norm of the error still improves during the following 40,000 iterations, which is necessary in order to

satisfy the stopping criterion.

For $\beta = 0.99$, i.e. Figure 4.2, the function value already starts oscillating around the optimal solution after a few iterations with a continuously decreasing amplitude. The norm of the error oscillates around a decreasing trend with an upper bound that seems almost linear.

Note that the jump that occurs in each plot during the first iterations is caused by the choice of starting vectors.

Figure 4.2: Plots for $\beta = 0.99$ and $\tau = \sigma = 0.4$

4.2 Power Plant Operation Planning

In this section we use the results of Chapter 3 to solve a problem that is motivated by the challenges induced by the integration of renewable energy sources into the power system. Obviously, many renewable energy sources are subject to uncertainties as the amount of wind or the hours of sunlight during the day. Due to this stochastic nature, *traditional market clearing mechanisms are no longer optimal* (cf. [BPP16, Page 1]). Therefore, W. A. Bukhsh, A. Papakonstantinou and P. Pinson developed a risk-aware market clearing strategy for an electricity grid with a significant amount of energy from renewable sources (cf. [BPP16]). They proposed an electricity market that accepts probabilistic offers and used the Conditional Value-at-Risk to evaluate the risk of high re-dispatching cost due to the mis-estimation of renewable energy (*re-dispatching refers to a request issued by the transmission system operator to power plants to adjust the real power they input in order to avoid or eliminate congestion**). We adopt their model and apply Algorithm 3.2 to solve the resulting optimization problem.

4.2.1 Problem Formulation

In this section we formally describe the optimization problem developed by W. A. Bukhsh, A. Papakonstantinou and P. Pinson in [BPP16]. Although we adopt most notations and ideas, some of them are modified in order to overcome some mathematical inaccuracies. We also elaborate on some terminology that might be unfamiliar to the reader without any educational background in power systems engineering.

The model is based on a two-stage stochastic programming problem (cf. Section 2.2.2). The conceptual framework can be described as follows: a transmission system operator (TSO) has to clear the day-ahead market and therefore determine the commitment of conventional power

*cf. TransnetBW, January 2018, URL: <https://www.transnetbw.com/en/energy-market/ancillary-services/redispatch>

plants. The producers of renewable energy are asked to submit probabilistic offers in form of probability distributions. The resulting day-ahead generation schedule represents the first stage of the problem and seeks to minimize the total cost of power generation (note that we consider the day ahead as one time period only). In the second stage, when the TSO has full information about the random event (i.e. the amount of energy generated from renewable sources), corrective actions are taken, including rescheduling of the conventional power plants or curtailment of the renewables (in the case of wind energy, curtailment could for example mean pitching one or more rotor blades in order to change the angle of attack of the air on the blades). The inherent risk of over-committing expensive conventional generators versus under-utilization of cheap and clean generation from renewable sources is measured by the CVaR.

The transmission network we want to model can be described by a graph consisting of nodes that are connected by edges. In our framework, the nodes are referred to as *buses* and the edges as *lines*. Figure 4.3 shows the grid we will use for our simulation. It consists of six conventional generators and three wind farms, and was derived from the New England test case in [ZMT11]. The exact modifications are described in Section 4.2.2. Note that, for the sake of simplicity, we incorporate wind as the only renewable energy source, even though the theoretical model is capable of handling other sources (e.g. solar energy) as well.

The following subsections explain the components of our model.

Sets

Several sets are used to describe the model. They are all denoted by calligraphic upper-case letters and defined as follows.

\mathcal{B}	Buses, i.e. the nodes in Figure 4.3.	\mathcal{B}_l	Buses connected by line $l \in \mathcal{L}$.
\mathcal{L}	Lines, i.e. the edges in Figure 4.3; every line has a start- and an end-bus.	\mathcal{L}_b^\pm	Lines starting(-)/ending(+) at bus $b \in \mathcal{B}$.
\mathcal{G}	Generators, i.e. conventional power plants.	\mathcal{G}_b	Generators located at bus $b \in \mathcal{B}$.
\mathcal{W}	Wind farms.	\mathcal{W}_b	Wind farms located at bus $b \in \mathcal{B}$.
\mathcal{S}	Scenarios.		

Figure 4.3: 39-bus network; adapted from [BPP16, Figure 1]

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Variables

The variables can change during the process of optimization and are therefore stated together with the respective feasible set. All variables are written in lower-case or Greek letters.

First-Stage Variables

u_g	$\in \{0, 1\}$	Unit commitment variable; specifies if the conventional generator $g \in \mathcal{G}$ is on or off.
p_g^G	$\in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$	Real power output of generator $g \in \mathcal{G}$.

Second-Stage Variables

$p_{w,s}^W$	$\in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$	Real power output of wind farm $w \in \mathcal{W}$ in scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$.
$p_{l,s}^L$	$\in \mathbb{R}$	Real power flow through line $l \in \mathcal{L}$ in scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$; if the direction of flow is equal to the direction of the line, $p_{l,s}^L$ is positive; otherwise, it is negative.
$\theta_{b,s}$	$\in [0, 2\pi]$	Voltage angle at bus $b \in \mathcal{B}$ in scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$.
$\Delta p_{g,s}^G$	$\in \mathbb{R}$	Regulation of conventional generator $g \in \mathcal{G}$.
$\Delta p_{g,s}^{G\pm}$	$\in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$	Downward(-)/upward(+) regulation of conventional generator $g \in \mathcal{G}$.

Note that the unit commitment variables are assumed to be binary in order to represent the commitment of the related generators. However, we can not model this restriction with the methods described in [Chapter 3](#) and therefore relax it to get $u_g \in [0, 1]$ for all $g \in \mathcal{G}$. This modification still allows us to integrate the described algorithm into a branch-and-bound framework (cf. [BT97, Chapter 11.2]) that guarantees the integrality of the unit commitment variables.

Parameters

The parameters represent the given data and do not change during the process of optimization. They are all written in upper-case or Greek letters.

η_l	Susceptance of line $l \in \mathcal{L}$.
P_l^{\max}	Power capacity of line $l \in \mathcal{L}$.
P_b^D	Real power demand at bus $b \in \mathcal{B}$.
$P_g^{G\pm}$	Minimum(-)/maximum(+) real power output of conventional generator $g \in \mathcal{G}$.
P_w^{W+}	Maximum real power output of wind farm $w \in \mathcal{W}$ due to technical limitations.
$\xi_{w,s}$	Realization of the random variable $\hat{\xi}$ (cf. definition of constraint (4.2.1)) such that $\xi_{w,s} P_w^{W+}$ is the maximum possible real power output of wind farm $w \in \mathcal{W}$ in scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$.
C_g^{VAR}	Variable costs of generator $g \in \mathcal{G}$.
C_g^{FIX}	Fixed costs, i.e. costs of committing generator $g \in \mathcal{G}$.
$C_g^{R\pm}$	Costs of downward(-)/upward(+) regulation of generator $g \in \mathcal{G}$.
C_w^{PP}	Purchase price of power at wind farm $w \in \mathcal{W}$.

R_g^\pm	Maximum downward(-)/upward(+) regulation of generator $g \in \mathcal{G}$.
β	Probability level of the CVaR.
γ	Weight of the CVaR in the objective function.

Constraints

In order to understand the restrictions on wind power output, we first need to describe how the uncertain production is being modeled. Every wind farm $w \in \mathcal{W}$ has an upper production limit P_w^{W+} due to technical limitations. We express the real upper bound in scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$ as $\xi_{w,s} P_w^{W+}$, where $\xi_{w,s} \in [0, 1]$ is a realization of the random variable $\hat{\xi}_w : \Omega \rightarrow [0, 1]$ (cf. Definition 2.2.1). This random variable follows a distribution Ξ defined by a set of parameters λ_w (e.g. mean and variance) such that $\hat{\xi}_w \sim \Xi(\lambda_w)$. If we also consider the possibility of curtailment as mentioned in the introduction of Section 4.2.1, we get the constraint

$$0 \leq p_{w,s}^W \leq \xi_{w,s} P_w^{W+} \quad (4.2.1)$$

for every wind farm $w \in \mathcal{W}$ and every scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$.

The real power output of a conventional generator $g \in \mathcal{G}$ is determined in two stages. In the first stage it is decided whether the generator will be on or off and how much power it will produce. In the second stage, i.e. when the amount of renewable energy is known, the exact output can be varied by regulating the generator up- or downward. This regulation for scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$ is subject to the following restrictions:

$$\Delta p_{g,s}^G = \Delta p_{g,s}^{G+} - \Delta p_{g,s}^{G-}, \quad (4.2.2a)$$

$$0 \leq \Delta p_{g,s}^{G+} \leq R_g^+, \quad (4.2.2b)$$

$$0 \leq \Delta p_{g,s}^{G-} \leq R_g^-. \quad (4.2.2c)$$

Furthermore, to make sure that the generated power lies within the defined bounds, we impose the restriction

$$P_g^{G-} u_g \leq p_g^G + \Delta p_{g,s}^G \leq P_g^{G+} u_g, \quad (4.2.3)$$

which, at the same time, enforces that the generated power can only be different from zero if the generator is turned on.

Obviously, since we do not model any energy storage or connection to another network, the generated power within the grid must exactly match the demand. This induces the following power balance equation for every bus $b \in \mathcal{B}$ and scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$\sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}_b} (p_g^G + \Delta p_{g,s}^G) + \sum_{w \in \mathcal{W}_b} p_{w,s}^W = P_b^D + \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}_b^-} p_{l,s}^L - \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}_b^+} p_{l,s}^L. \quad (4.2.4)$$

The left-hand side represents the total power generated at bus b including the up- and downward regulation of the conventional generators. The right-hand side sums up the demand at bus b and the power flow through all lines connected to this bus, depending on the direction of the respective line/edge (cf. definition of variable $p_{l,s}^L$ in Section 4.2.1).

The power flow depends on the voltage angles at the buses connected by the respective line. If we use the DC model of power flow as in [Moh11, A.2], the lines are assumed to be lossless and the constraint can be written as

$$p_{l,s}^L = -\eta_l (\theta_{b,s} - \theta_{b',s}), \quad (4.2.5)$$

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where $s \in \mathcal{S}$, $b, b' \in \mathcal{B}$ and $l \in \mathcal{L}_b^- \cap \mathcal{L}_{b'}^+$, i.e. line l starts at bus b and ends at bus b' . For further explanations regarding the terms *susceptance* (η_l) and *voltage angle* ($\theta_{b,s}$) we refer to specialized literature, for example [Gli11].

Another restriction that is imposed on the power flow is the capacity of the lines, i.e.

$$-P_l^{\max} \leq p_{l,s}^l \leq P_l^{\max} \quad (4.2.6)$$

for every line $l \in \mathcal{L}$ and every scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$.

Now that we know the constraints of our optimization problem, we need to write them all together as one inequality $Bx \leq b$. This is necessary for the input of [Algorithm 3.2](#) but pretty straightforward work and therefore described in the [Appendix B.1](#).

Objective Function

The objective is minimizing the cost of generation from the conventional generators while optimally utilizing the renewable energy. The day-ahead cost of generator $g \in \mathcal{G}$ is given as

$$C_g^{\text{DA}}(p_g^G, u_g) := C_g^{\text{VAR}} p_g^G + C_g^{\text{FIX}} u_g. \quad (4.2.7)$$

The cost of regulation in scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$ is defined as

$$C_{g,s}^{\text{REG}}(\Delta p_{g,s}^G) := C_g^{R+} \Delta p_{g,s}^{G+} + C_g^{R-} \Delta p_{g,s}^{G-}. \quad (4.2.8)$$

In order to incorporate the risk measure CVaR, we need to define the value of the loss-function (cf. [Section 2.3.1](#)) for every scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$. Let

$$z_s := z_s((p_{w,s}^W)_{w \in \mathcal{W}}) := \sum_{w \in \mathcal{W}} C_w^{\text{PP}} (\xi_{w,s} P_w^{W+} - p_{w,s}^W) \quad (4.2.9)$$

for all $s \in \mathcal{S}$. Recall that $\xi_{w,s} P_w^{W+}$ denotes the power that could be generated due to the prevailing weather conditions, and $p_{w,s}^W$ is the power that is actually being utilized at wind farm $w \in \mathcal{W}$ for scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$. Then, z_s can be interpreted as the imaginary cost or penalty for curtailing wind energy production in scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$. We use the term *imaginary* here to emphasize that our model does not implement the actual purchase of power, e.g. at a spot market. Since we use scenarios to discretize the distributions, we can express the CVaR in accordance with [Definition 2.3.4](#) as

$$\text{CVaR}_\beta(z, p) = \min_{\alpha \in \mathbb{R}} \left(\alpha + (|\mathcal{S}|(1 - \beta))^{-1} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} [z_s - \alpha]^+ \right), \quad (4.2.10)$$

where $z := z((p_{w,s}^W)_{w \in \mathcal{W}, s \in \mathcal{S}}) := (z_s)_{s \in \mathcal{S}}$ as defined in (4.2.9) and $p := (|\mathcal{S}|^{-1}, \dots, |\mathcal{S}|^{-1})$, i.e. all scenarios are assumed to be equally likely.

If we combine (4.2.7), (4.2.8) and (4.2.10) and weight the regulation cost with the scenario probability $|\mathcal{S}|^{-1}$ of the respective scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$, we get the following objective function:

$$\sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \left(C_g^{\text{DA}}(p_g^G, u_g) + |\mathcal{S}|^{-1} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} C_{g,s}^{\text{REG}}(\Delta p_{g,s}^G) \right) + \gamma \text{CVaR}_\beta(z, p). \quad (4.2.11)$$

A reformulation of this objective function that has the same structure as in (3.1.1) can be found in the [Appendix B.2](#).

4.2.2 Data

In this section we describe which data is used for the computations and how it is modified. As mentioned in the introduction of Section 4.2.1, the data originates from the New England test case in MATPOWER, which is described in [ZMT11]. In order to incorporate renewable energy sources, the conventional generators 33, 34 and 36 (cf. Figure 4.3) are replaced by wind farms with twice the capacity of the replaced generators.

In the following we describe how the values of the parameters defined in Section 4.2.1 are calculated and which assumptions underlie these calculations.

- The susceptance η_l of a transmission line $l \in \mathcal{L}$ is assumed to be the inverse value of the line's reactance, as described in [Moh11, A.2]. Since MATPOWER uses degrees as angle measure, this susceptance is then multiplied by $\frac{360}{2\pi}$.
- The power capacity P_l^{\max} of a transmission line $l \in \mathcal{L}$ is assumed to be equal to its susceptance multiplied by $\frac{\pi}{8}$. This factor is chosen such that the voltage angle difference in equation (4.2.5) is *small enough*, which is an assumption of the DC model of power flow in [Moh11, A.2].
- As explained in the definition of constraint (4.2.1), the upper production limit P_w^{W+} of a wind farm $w \in \mathcal{W}$ in scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$ is equal to $\xi_{w,s} P_w^{W+}$, where $\xi_{w,s} \in [0, 1]$ is a realization of the random variable $\hat{\xi}_w \sim \Xi(\lambda_w)$, which is defined by a set of parameters λ_w . This uncertainty is modeled by a Beta distribution with mean $\mu := 0.55$ and variance $\sigma^2 := 0.05$ (cf. [BPP16, Chapter V]). The parameters α and β are given by

$$\alpha := \frac{(1-\mu)\mu^2}{\sigma^2} - \mu \quad \text{and} \quad \beta := \frac{(1-\mu)\alpha}{\mu}, \quad (4.2.12)$$

such that $\lambda_w := (\alpha, \beta)$ for all $w \in \mathcal{W}$.

- The variable and fixed costs of the conventional generators are given in MATPOWER. However, since MATPOWER models every hour of the day ahead, this costs must be multiplied by 24 to cover the whole day.
- The costs of up-regulation are assumed to be 10% higher and the costs of down-regulation 9% lower than the variable costs (cf. [BPP16, Chapter V]).
- The maximum downward/upward regulation of the conventional generators are assumed to be 20% of their production capacity.
- The purchase price C_w^{PP} at wind farm $w \in \mathcal{W}$ is assumed to be the maximum of upward regulation costs across all conventional generators, i.e. $C_w^{\text{PP}} = \max \{ C_g^{R+} \mid g \in \mathcal{G} \}$.

4.2.3 Numerical Results

Figures 4.4 and 4.5 show the behavior of Algorithm 3.2 when converging to the optimal solution. This optimal solution is computed by the `linprog`-method of MATLAB, which is applied to a linearized formulation of the model (analogously to [RU00, Chapter 3]). The number of scenarios is equal to 10 in Figure 4.4 and equal to 100 in Figure 4.5. In both figures the probability level β is set to 0.9. Subfigure (a) displays the function value per iteration in blue and the `linprog`-solution in red. Subfigure (b) shows the maximum infeasibility per iteration, which is at iteration $k \in \mathbb{N}$ defined as

$$\max_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \left\{ \max \{ B_i x^k - b_i, 0 \} \right\}. \quad (4.2.13)$$

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The parameters τ and σ are chosen such that they are equal and close to $\|K\|^{-1}$ but still satisfy the convergence criterion in Section 3.4. This is implemented as $\tau := \sigma := (1 - \varepsilon)\|K\|^{-1}$ with $\varepsilon := 10^{-2}$, which implies $\tau\sigma\|K\|^2 = (1 - \varepsilon)^2 < 1$.

Figure 4.4: Plots for $|S| = 10$, $\beta = 0.9$, and $\tau = \sigma \approx 2.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$

Both figures show that the values of the objective function converge to the respective optimal solution. For $|S| = 10$, a good approximation is reached after about $0.8 \cdot 10^8$ iterations. However, at this iteration, the maximum infeasibility lies between 100 and 10 and is still following a decreasing trend. The same behavior can be observed for $|S| = 100$, where the function value converges a bit faster and reaches a good approximation after about $0.5 \cdot 10^8$ iterations. At this point, the maximum infeasibility is less than 10 and also still following a decreasing trend.

Figure 4.5: Plots for $|S| = 100$, $\beta = 0.9$, and $\tau = \sigma \approx 2.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$

In conclusion one can say that Figures 4.4 and 4.5 suggest that Algorithm 3.2 works properly and finds the optimal solution. However, the performance in both test cases was inferior compared to the linearized version solved by linprog. On a 2.6 GHz Intel i5 machine, both computations of Algorithm 3.2 took more than 24 hours and were terminated at iteration 10^8 (i.e. no other stopping criterion was satisfied).

5 Concluding Remarks

The numerical analysis in Sections 4.1.3 and 4.2.3 show that the performance of Algorithm 3.2 in terms of computation time is inferior compared to the `linprog`-method of MATLAB applied to the linearized models. Apart from improving the implementation such that less computation time is needed, there might be optimization problems that are more suitable. Therefore, further research could be focused on problems that are more complicated in the sense that they can not be written equivalently as linear programs, for example if they involve partial differential equations.

Another idea is related to the integrality of the unit commitment variables in the power plant operation planning model (cf. Section 4.2). Instead of just relaxing the integrality condition and incorporating the whole algorithm into a branch-and-bound framework, one could introduce a penalty term to the objective function. This penalty term is the integral over a functional that depends on the real power output of the conventional generators and replaces constraint (4.2.3). It is defined such that it is linear below the minimum power output and quadratic above. The idea of this approach is explained in more detail in [CK16].

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Appendices

Appendix A Improvement of the Projection Algorithm

In this chapter we elaborate on how [Algorithm 3.1](#) can be improved in order to save computation time.

Note that finding τ in [Line 2](#) of [Algorithm 3.1](#) could take a great share of the computation time, especially if it is done by simply checking the condition $jp + \sum_{i=j+1}^n \max\{0, u_i + p - u_j\} \leq 1$ for every $j \in \{0, \dots, n\}$, starting at $j = 0$ and terminating if the condition is not satisfied any more. Certainly, the actual computational cost depends on the given input y and p , but yet it is reasonable to use a smarter way of finding τ .

Algorithm A.1 (Find tau)

Input: $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, $z : \{m, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ non-decreasing

```

1 if  $z(m) > 1$  then  $\tau \leftarrow m - 1$ 
2 else if  $z(n) \leq 1$  then  $\tau \leftarrow n$ 
3 else if  $m + 1 = n$  then  $\tau \leftarrow m$ 
4 else
5   Calculate  $j \leftarrow m + \lfloor \frac{n-m}{2} \rfloor$ .
6   Run the algorithm again with  $\{m, \dots, j\}$  as the domain of  $z$ ; the solution is
   denoted by  $k$ .
7   if  $k = j$  then
8     Run the algorithm again with  $\{j + 1, \dots, n\}$  as the domain of  $z$ ; the solution
     is denoted by  $l$ .
9     if  $l = j$  then  $\tau \leftarrow k$ 
10    else  $\tau \leftarrow l$ 
11  else  $\tau \leftarrow k$ 
12 end

```

Output: τ

Let us assume that we want to find the greatest integer $j \in \{m, \dots, n\}$ ($m, n \in \mathbb{N}$) such that $z(j) \leq 1$, where $z : \{m, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a non-decreasing function. In our framework, z would be defined as

$$j \mapsto z(j) := jp + \sum_{i=j+1}^n \max\{0, u_i + p - u_j\}. \quad (\text{A.0.1})$$

With inequality (3.3.27) we showed that z is indeed non-increasing. The recursive [Algorithm A.1](#) is a very simple solution that performs much better in *most cases* (i.e. if we assume that τ can be equally likely any integer from 0 to n). [Lines 1](#) to [3](#) handle some trivial cases. Then the domain of z is cut in two halves (cf. [Line 5](#)) and the algorithm is run again with the lower half as the domain of z (cf. [Line 6](#)). If the solution k is not equal to the new upper bound j , it must be the

final solution (cf. Line 11). Otherwise, the final solution is either k itself or it lies in the upper half of the domain, i.e. in $\{j + 1, \dots, n\}$. This is checked by running the algorithm again with the upper half as the domain of z (cf. Line 8). Note that $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ denotes the function of rounding down to the next integer that is less or equal to the argument. An implementation in MATLAB can be found in the Appendix C as MATLAB-Code C.1.2.

In anticipation of the final algorithm of Section 3.4, we can make another improvement that speeds Algorithm 3.1 up if it is called multiple times in a row. In this case, it is reasonable to assume that the input of Algorithm 3.1 is not significantly different from the input of the previous function call. Therefore, the index τ is likely to change only slightly from one call to the next one. Algorithm A.2 enables us to pass an initial guess of τ and iterate up- or downward until the real τ is found. However, if no initial guess is provided, it just calls Algorithm A.1. An implementation in MATLAB can be found in the Appendix C as MATLAB-Code C.1.3.

Algorithm A.2 (Find tau with an initial guess)

Input: $u \in \mathbb{R}^n$ s.t. $u_1 \geq \dots \geq u_n$, $p \geq \frac{1}{n}$, *optional:* initial guess $\tau_0 \in \{1, \dots, n\}$

```

1 Define  $z(j) := jp + \sum_{i=j+1}^n \max\{0, u_i + p - u_j\}$  for every  $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ .
2 if  $\tau_0$  is empty then
3   | Call Algorithm A.1 with  $z : \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$  and denote the solution by  $\tau$ .
4 else
5   |  $\tau_1 \leftarrow \tau_0$ 
6   | while true do
7     | if  $z(\tau_1) \leq 1$  then
8       |    $\tau \leftarrow \tau_1$ 
9       |    $\tau_1 \leftarrow \tau_1 + 1$ 
10    | else
11    |   if the previous if-condition was true during the last iteration then break
12    |   else
13    |     |  $\tau_1 \leftarrow \tau_1 - 1$ 
14    |     | if  $\tau_1 > 0$  then  $\tau \leftarrow \tau_1$ 
15    |     | else break
16    |     | end
17    |   end
18  | end
19 end

Output:  $\tau$ 

```

Appendix B Reformulation of the Model for Power Plant Operation Planning

In this chapter we describe how we rewrite the constraints and the objective function of [Section 4.2.1](#) to get an optimization problem that has the same structure as [\(3.1.1\)](#). This is necessary for the input of [Algorithm 3.2](#).

B.1 Constraints

The constraints of [Section 4.2.1](#) need to be written as an inequality of the form $Bx \leq b$.

Let us first define the column vector

$$p^W := \left((p_{w,s}^W)_{w \in \mathcal{W}} \right)_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \quad (\text{B.1.1})$$

$$:= (p_{1,1}^W, \dots, p_{|\mathcal{W}|,1}^W, p_{1,2}^W, \dots, p_{|\mathcal{W}|,2}^W, \dots, p_{1,|\mathcal{S}|}^W, \dots, p_{|\mathcal{W}|,|\mathcal{S}|}^W), \quad (\text{B.1.2})$$

where $|\mathcal{M}|$ denotes the cardinality of set \mathcal{M} . With this notation, we furthermore define

$$\Delta p^{G^+} := \left((\Delta p_{g,s}^{G^+})_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \right)_{s \in \mathcal{S}}, \quad (\text{B.1.3})$$

$$\Delta p^{G^-} := \left((\Delta p_{g,s}^{G^-})_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \right)_{s \in \mathcal{S}}, \quad (\text{B.1.4})$$

$$p^G := (p_g^G)_{g \in \mathcal{G}}, \quad (\text{B.1.5})$$

$$u := (u_g)_{g \in \mathcal{G}}, \quad (\text{B.1.6})$$

$$p^L := \left((p_{l,s}^L)_{l \in \mathcal{L}} \right)_{s \in \mathcal{S}}, \quad (\text{B.1.7})$$

$$\theta := \left((\theta_{b,s})_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \right)_{s \in \mathcal{S}}. \quad (\text{B.1.8})$$

If we use the notation $\xi P^{W^+} := \left((\xi_{w,s} P_w^{W^+})_{w \in \mathcal{W}} \right)_{s \in \mathcal{S}}$, constraint [\(4.2.1\)](#) can be written as

$$\begin{cases} -E_{|\mathcal{W}||\mathcal{S}|} p^W & \leq \mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{W}||\mathcal{S}|}, \\ E_{|\mathcal{W}||\mathcal{S}|} p^W & \leq \xi P^{W^+}, \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.1.9})$$

where $E_{|\mathcal{W}||\mathcal{S}|}$ denotes the identity matrix of dimension $|\mathcal{W}||\mathcal{S}| \times |\mathcal{W}||\mathcal{S}|$ and $\mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{W}||\mathcal{S}|}$ the zero vector of length $|\mathcal{W}||\mathcal{S}|$.

To reformulate constraint [\(4.2.2\)](#), we use equation [\(4.2.2a\)](#) to eliminate the variable $\Delta p_{g,s}^G$. Equations [\(4.2.2b\)](#) and [\(4.2.2c\)](#) can then be written as

$$\begin{cases} -E_{|\mathcal{G}||\mathcal{S}|} \Delta p^{G^+} & \leq \mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{G}||\mathcal{S}|}, \\ E_{|\mathcal{G}||\mathcal{S}|} \Delta p^{G^+} & \leq \begin{pmatrix} R^+ \\ \vdots \\ R^+ \end{pmatrix}, \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.1.10})$$

and

$$\begin{cases} -E_{|\mathcal{G}||\mathcal{S}} \Delta p^{G^-} \leq \mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{G}||\mathcal{S}|}, \\ E_{|\mathcal{G}||\mathcal{S}} \Delta p^{G^-} \leq \begin{pmatrix} R^- \\ \vdots \\ R^- \end{pmatrix}, \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.1.11})$$

with $R^+ := (R_g^+)_{g \in \mathcal{G}}$ and $R^- := (R_g^-)_{g \in \mathcal{G}}$.

Constraint (4.2.3) is equivalent to

$$\begin{pmatrix} \vdots & \vdots & E_{|\mathcal{G}|} & -\text{diag}(P^{G^+}) \\ E_{|\mathcal{G}||\mathcal{S}|} & -E_{|\mathcal{G}||\mathcal{S}|} & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & E_{|\mathcal{G}|} & -\text{diag}(P^{G^+}) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Delta p^{G^+} \\ \Delta p^{G^-} \\ p^G \\ u \end{pmatrix} \leq \mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{G}||\mathcal{S}|} \quad (\text{B.1.12})$$

and

$$\begin{pmatrix} \vdots & \vdots & -E_{|\mathcal{G}|} & \text{diag}(P^{G^-}) \\ -E_{|\mathcal{G}||\mathcal{S}|} & E_{|\mathcal{G}||\mathcal{S}|} & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & -E_{|\mathcal{G}|} & \text{diag}(P^{G^-}) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Delta p^{G^+} \\ \Delta p^{G^-} \\ p^G \\ u \end{pmatrix} \leq \mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{G}||\mathcal{S}|}, \quad (\text{B.1.13})$$

where $P^{G^+} := (P_g^{G^+})_{g \in \mathcal{G}}$, $P^{G^-} := (P_g^{G^-})_{g \in \mathcal{G}}$ and $\text{diag}(\cdot)$ is a diagonal matrix with the elements of the argument as the main diagonal.

In order to rewrite constraint (4.2.4), we first have to define the following three incidence matrices that describe

- which conventional generator is located at which bus:

$$A^G := (a_{ij}^G)_{\substack{i=1,\dots,|\mathcal{B}| \\ j=1,\dots,|\mathcal{G}|}} \quad \text{with} \quad a_{ij}^G := \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } j \in \mathcal{G}_i, \\ 0, & \text{else;} \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.1.14})$$

- which wind farm is located at which bus:

$$A^W := (a_{ij}^W)_{\substack{i=1,\dots,|\mathcal{B}| \\ j=1,\dots,|\mathcal{W}|}} \quad \text{with} \quad a_{ij}^W := \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } j \in \mathcal{W}_i, \\ 0, & \text{else;} \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.1.15})$$

- which lines are connected to which buses and in which direction:

$$A^L := (a_{ij}^L)_{\substack{i=1,\dots,|\mathcal{B}| \\ j=1,\dots,|\mathcal{L}|}} \quad \text{with} \quad a_{ij}^L := \begin{cases} -1, & \text{if } j \in \mathcal{L}_i^-, \\ 1, & \text{if } j \in \mathcal{L}_i^+, \\ 0, & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.1.16})$$

With this and $P^D := (P_b^D)_{b \in \mathcal{B}}$, we can write equation (4.2.4) as

$$\begin{pmatrix} \vdots \\ A_{\times|S}^W & A_{\times|S}^G & -A_{\times|S}^G & A^G & A_{\times|S}^L \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} p^W \\ \Delta p^{G+} \\ \Delta p^{G-} \\ p^G \\ p^L \end{pmatrix} \leq P^D \quad (\text{B.1.17})$$

and

$$\begin{pmatrix} \vdots \\ -A_{\times|S}^W & -A_{\times|S}^G & A_{\times|S}^G & -A^G & -A_{\times|S}^L \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} p^W \\ \Delta p^{G+} \\ \Delta p^{G-} \\ p^G \\ p^L \end{pmatrix} \leq -P^D, \quad (\text{B.1.18})$$

where $A_{\times|S} := A \cdots A$ is the notation for matrix A written $|S|$ -times in a row.

Let $\tilde{A}^L := (A^L \text{diag}((\eta_l)_{l \in \mathcal{L}}))^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{L}| \times |\mathcal{B}|}$. Then the power flow equation (4.2.5) is equivalent to

$$\begin{pmatrix} \vdots \\ E_{|\mathcal{L}||S} & \vdots & -\tilde{A}^L \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} p^L \\ \theta \end{pmatrix} \leq \mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{L}||S|} \quad (\text{B.1.19})$$

and

$$\begin{pmatrix} \vdots \\ -E_{|\mathcal{L}||S} & \vdots & \tilde{A}^L \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} p^L \\ \theta \end{pmatrix} \leq \mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{L}||S|}, \quad (\text{B.1.20})$$

where the matrices in the right-hand column occur $|S|$ -times.

The capacity of the lines is modeled in (4.2.6) and can be equivalently expressed as

$$\begin{cases} -E_{|\mathcal{L}||S} p^L \leq \begin{pmatrix} p^{\max} \\ \vdots \\ p^{\max} \end{pmatrix}, \\ E_{|\mathcal{L}||S} p^L \leq \begin{pmatrix} p^{\max} \\ \vdots \\ p^{\max} \end{pmatrix}, \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.1.21})$$

where $p^{\max} := (p_l^{\max})_{l \in \mathcal{L}}$.

The only constraints we have not modeled yet are the feasible sets of the variables defined in Section 4.2.1. The restrictions on p_g^G , $p_{w,s}^W$, $\Delta p_{g,s}^{G+}$ and $\Delta p_{g,s}^{G-}$ for all $g \in \mathcal{G}$, $w \in \mathcal{W}$ and $s \in \mathcal{S}$ are implicitly modeled within the previous constraints, whereas the unit commitment variable and the voltage angle require additional inequalities.

with $n := |S|(|\mathcal{W}| + 2|\mathcal{G}| + |\mathcal{L}| + |\mathcal{B}|) + 2|\mathcal{G}|$. The vertical dashed lines separate the variables and the horizontal dashed lines the constraints. Every empty rectangle is considered a matrix of all zeros.

B.2 Objective Function

The first part of the objective function (4.2.11), i.e. without CVaR, must be written as a linear function H such that $H(x) = h^\top x$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and an $h \in \mathbb{R}^n$ as in (3.1.1). If we use the notations

$$C^{R+} := \left(C_g^{R+} \mathbf{1}_{|S|} \right)_{g \in \mathcal{G}}, \quad (\text{B.2.1})$$

$$C^{R-} := \left(C_g^{R-} \mathbf{1}_{|S|} \right)_{g \in \mathcal{G}}, \quad (\text{B.2.2})$$

$$C^{\text{VAR}} := \left(C_g^{\text{VAR}} \right)_{g \in \mathcal{G}}, \quad (\text{B.2.3})$$

$$\text{and } C^{\text{FIX}} := \left(C_g^{\text{FIX}} \right)_{g \in \mathcal{G}}, \quad (\text{B.2.4})$$

and consider the order of the variables as defined in (B.1.25), we can easily see that

$$h = \left(\mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{W}||S|} \mid |S|^{-1} C^{R+} \mid |S|^{-1} C^{R-} \mid C^{\text{VAR}} \mid C^{\text{FIX}} \mid \mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{L}||S|} \mid \mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{B}||S|} \right)^\top. \quad (\text{B.2.5})$$

The argument of CVaR in (4.2.11) is denoted by $z = (z_s)_{s \in S}$ and defined as in (4.2.9) by

$$z_s := z_s \left((p_{w,s}^W)_{w \in \mathcal{W}} \right) := \sum_{w \in \mathcal{W}} C_w^{\text{PP}} \left(\xi_{w,s} P_w^{W+} - p_{w,s}^W \right). \quad (\text{B.2.6})$$

The structure of (3.1.1) requires that we define a matrix $D \in \mathbb{R}^{|S|} \times \mathbb{R}^n$ and a vector $v \in \mathbb{R}^{|S|}$ such that

$$z = Dx + v, \quad (\text{B.2.7})$$

where x is defined as in (B.1.25). Therefore, we define $D := (D_s)_{s \in S}$, where the row D_s of D belonging to scenario $s \in S$ is given by

$$D_s := \left(\mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{W}||(s-1)} \mid -C^{\text{PP}} \mid \mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{W}||(|S|-s)} \mid \mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{G}||S|} \mid \mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{G}||S|} \mid \mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{G}||S|} \mid \mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{G}||S|} \mid \mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{L}||S|} \mid \mathbf{0}_{|\mathcal{B}||S|} \right). \quad (\text{B.2.8})$$

We use the notation $C^{\text{PP}} := \left(C_w^{\text{PP}} \right)_{w \in \mathcal{W}}$ and assume without loss of generality that $S = \{1, \dots, d\}$ for a $d \in \mathbb{N}$. Together with $v := (v_s)_{s \in S}$ defined as

$$v_s := \sum_{w \in \mathcal{W}} C_w^{\text{PP}} \xi_{w,s} P_w^{W+} \quad (\text{B.2.9})$$

for all $s \in S$, equation (B.2.7) is satisfied.

Appendix C MATLAB-Code

In this chapter we present the MATLAB-Code of the algorithms developed throughout this thesis.

C.1 Primal-Dual Algorithm

MATLAB-Code C.1.1: "Projection onto the bounded probability simplex"

```

1 function [x, tau] = SimplexProj(y, p, tau_guess)
2 % Calculates the projection of the vector y onto the bounded probability
3 % simplex, i.e.
4 %   min(1/2*norm(x-y)^2) s.t. x.'1=1 and 0<=x<=p
5 % where p is a positive real number. It is possible to pass a guess of the
6 % value of tau.
7
8 %% Verify input.
9 if size(y, 2) == 1
10     y = y';
11 elseif size(y, 1) ~= 1
12     error('y must either be a column or a row vector.')
```

```

13 end
14 n = size(y, 2);
15 if p < 1/n
16     error('p must be greater than or equal to 1/n.')
```

```

17 end
18
19 %% Compute the projection.
20 % Sort y.
21 u = sort(y, 2, 'descend');
```

```

22
23 % Calculate tau.
24 lambda_found = 0;
25 [tau, z_tau] = FindTauGuess(u, p, tau_guess);
26 if z_tau == 1
27     lambda = p - u(tau);
28     lambda_found = 1;
29 end
30
31 % Calculate rho.
32 if not(lambda_found)
33     u_cum = 1 - tau*p - cumsum(u(tau+1:n));
34     if size(u, 1) == 1 && size(u, 2) == 1
35         rho = 1;
36     else
37         rho = tau + find(u(tau+1:n) + ...
38             bsxfun(@rdivide, u_cum(1:n-tau), 1:n-tau) > 0, 1, 'last');
```

```

39     end
40     lambda = u_cum(rho - tau)/(rho - tau);
41 end
42
43 % Calculate x and return a column vector.
44 x = transpose(max(0, min(y + lambda, p)));
45
46 end
```

MATLAB-Code C.1.2: "Find tau"

```

1 function [tau, z_tau] = FindTau(z, m, n, z_m, z_n)
2 % Calculates the greatest index tau in {m,...,n} such that z(tau)<=1.
3 % z has to be the function handle of a non-increasing function. In order to
4 % save computation time, the function values z_m and z_n of the interval
5 % bounds m and n can be passed. However, they are not necessary.
6 % If even z(m) is > 1, tau will be m - 1.
7
8 %% Verify input and handle trivial cases.
9 if m > n
10     error('m cannot be greater than n.')
11 end
12 if isempty(z_m)
13     z_m = z(m);
14 end
15 if z_m > 1
16     tau = m - 1;
17     z_tau = [];
18     return
19 end
20 if isempty(z_n)
21     z_n = z(n);
22 end
23 if z_n <= 1
24     tau = n;
25     z_tau = z_n;
26     return
27 end
28 if m + 1 == n
29     tau = m;
30     z_tau = z_m;
31     return
32 end
33
34 %% Cut the domain of 'z' into two halves and rerun the algorithm.
35 j = m + ceil((n - m)/2);
36 [k, z_k] = FindTau(z, m, j, z_m, []);
37 if k == j
38     [l, z_l] = FindTau(z, j+1, n, [], z_n);
39     if l == j
40         tau = k;
41         z_tau = z_k;
42         return
43     else
44         tau = l;
45         z_tau = z_l;
46         return
47     end
48 else
49     tau = k;
50     z_tau = z_k;
51     return
52 end
53
54 end

```

MATLAB-Code C.1.3: "Find tau with an initial guess"

```

1 function [tau, z_tau] = FindTauGuess(u, p, tau_guess)
2 % Calculates the greatest index tau such that z(tau) <= 1, where
3 % z(j) = sum(max(0, u(j+1:n) + p - u(j))) + j*p. The vector u has n entries
4 % and needs to be in a descending order. tau_guess can be provided as the
5 % starting point of the search in order to speed up the algorithm. However,
6 % if no tau_guess is given, the function FindTau is called.
7
8 %% Verify input.
9 if size(u, 1) == 1
10     u = u';
11 elseif size(u, 2) ~= 1
12     error('u must either be a column or a row vector.')
```

```

13 end
14 n = size(u, 1);
15
16 %% Initialize variables.
17 tau = [];
18 z_tau = [];
19 z = @(j) sum(max(0, u(j+1:n) + p - u(j))) + j*p;
20 if tau_guess > 0
21     tau = tau_guess;
22     z_tau = z(tau);
23 end
24 z_tau_new = z_tau;
25 flag = 0;
26
27 %% Find tau.
28 if isempty(tau)
29     [tau, z_tau] = FindTau(z, 1, n, [], []);
30 else
31     while true
32         if z_tau_new <= 1
33             % The final tau must be >= the current tau.
34             z_tau = z_tau_new;
35             tau = tau + 1;
36             z_tau_new = z(tau);
37             flag = 1;
38         else
39             tau = tau - 1;
40             if flag
41                 break
42             else
43                 if tau > 0
44                     z_tau_new = z(tau);
45                 else
46                     % We always have z(0) = 0.
47                     z_tau = 0;
48                     break
49                 end
50             end
51         end
52     end
53 end
```

MATLAB-Code C.1.4: "Solving the original problem"

```

1 function [x, y] = PrimalDualAlgo(B, b, S, D, v, h, beta, gamma, tau, ...
2     sigma, x, y, eps)
3 % Solves the original problem
4 % min(H(x) + gamma*CVaR_beta(Dx + v, p)) s.t. B*x <= b.
5
6 %% Verify input.
7 if size(y, 1) == 1
8     y = y';
9 elseif size(y, 2) ~= 1
10    error('y must either be a column or a row vector.')

```

```

59 p = 1/(S*(1 - beta));
60 diff_x_old = 0; diff_y_1_old = 0; diff_y_2_old = 0;
61
62 % Check if the convergence criterion is satisfied.
63 conv_crit = sigma*tau*normest(K)^2;
64 fprintf('sigma*tau*normest(K)^2=%s\n', conv_crit);
65
66 %% Solve the problem.
67 while true
68     [y_1, last_tau_proj] = ...
69         SimplexProj(1/gamma*(y_1 + sigma*(D*x_bar + v)), p, last_tau_proj);
70     y_1 = gamma*y_1;
71     y_2 = y_2 + sigma*(B*x_bar - min(1/sigma*y_2 + B*x_bar, b));
72     x_new = x - tau*(K_adj*[y_1; y_2] + h);
73     x_bar = 2*x_new - x;
74     x = x_new;
75
76     % Check stopping criterion in every hundredth iteration.
77     if mod(k, 1e2) == 1
78         [y_1_new, last_tau_proj] = ...
79             SimplexProj(1/gamma*(y_1 + sigma*(D*x + v)), p, last_tau_proj);
80         diff_y_1 = norm(y_1 - gamma*y_1_new);
81         diff_y_2 = sigma*norm(B*x - min(1/sigma*y_2 + B*x, b));
82         diff_x = tau*norm(K_adj*[y_1; y_2] + h);
83         if diff_x < eps && diff_y_1 < eps && diff_y_2 < eps
84             break
85         end
86
87         % Check if any improvement has been made.
88         if diff_x == diff_x_old && diff_y_1 == diff_y_1_old && ...
89             diff_y_2 == diff_y_2_old
90             error('The algorithm failed!')
91         end
92         diff_x_old = diff_x; diff_y_1_old = diff_y_1; diff_y_2_old = diff_y_2;
93
94     end
95
96     if any(isnan([x; y_1; y_2]))
97         error('The algorithm failed!')
98     end
99 end
100
101 y = [y_1; y_2];
102
103 end

```

C.2 Portfolio Optimization

MATLAB-Code C.2.1: "Portfolio Optimization"

```

1  %% Initialization
2  % Number of samples
3  S = 1000;
4  % Minimum return
5  R = 0.011;
6  % Number of instruments
7  n = 3;
8  % Define mean and covariance matrix of the loss.
9  m = [0.01011110; 0.0043532; 0.0137058];
10 cov = [0.00324625 0.00022983 0.00420395; ...
11        0.00022983 0.00049937 0.00019247; ...
12        0.00420395 0.00019247 0.00764097];
13 % Initialize random number generator.
14 rng default
15 % Generate random numbers from a multivariate normal distribution.
16 r = mvnrnd(m, cov, S);
17
18 %% Define parameters for the primal-dual algorithm.
19 B = [-eye(n); ones(1, n); -ones(1, n); -m'];
20 b = [zeros(n, 1); 1; -1; -R];
21 D = -r;
22 v = zeros(S, 1);
23 beta = 0.9;
24 gamma = 1;
25 tau = 0.4;
26 sigma = 0.4;
27 h = zeros(n, 1);
28 x_0 = 1/n*ones(n, 1);
29 y_0 = zeros(S + n + 3, 1);
30 eps = 1e-6;
31
32 %% Solve the problem with the primal-dual algorithm.
33 fprintf('primal-dual algorithm:\n');
34 successful = 1;
35 try
36     [x, ~] = PrimalDualAlgo(B, b, S, D, v, h, beta, ...
37                             gamma, tau, sigma, x_0, y_0, eps);
38 catch ME
39     disp(ME)
40     successful = 0;
41 end
42 % Compute optimal CVaR.
43 if successful
44     cvar = CVaR(beta, D*x + v, 1/S);
45 end
46
47 %% Solve the problem with linprog.
48 fprintf('linprog:\n');
49 c = [1, zeros(1, n), 1/(S*(1 - beta))*ones(1, S)];
50 A = [0 -m' zeros(1, S); -ones(S, 1) -r -eye(S)];
51 a = [-R; zeros(S, 1)];
52 Aeq = [0 ones(1, n) zeros(1, S)];
53 aeq = 1;
54 lb = [-inf, zeros(1, n + S)];
55 [z, cvar_linprog] = linprog(c, A, a, Aeq, aeq, lb, []);
56 x_linprog = z(2:n+1);

```

C.3 Power Plant Operation Planning

MATLAB-Code C.3.1: "Power Plant Operation Planning"

```

1  %% Load data and prepare it for the input of the primal dual algorithm.
2  % Load case.
3  mpc = loadcase(case39);
4
5  % Find rows of conventional generators 33, 34 and 36.
6  rows_to_delete = ismember(mpc.gen(:, 1), [33, 34, 36]);
7  % Change them into wind farms with twice the capacity.
8  % First column = bus number, second column = maximum real power output.
9  wind = [mpc.gen(rows_to_delete, 1), 2*mpc.gen(rows_to_delete, 9)];
10 % Delete the conventional generators.
11 mpc.gen = mpc.gen(not(rows_to_delete), :);
12 mpc.gencost = mpc.gencost(not(rows_to_delete), :);
13
14 % Number of wind farms.
15 num_W = size(wind, 1);
16 % Number of conventional generators.
17 num_G = size(mpc.gen, 1);
18 % Number of buses.
19 num_B = size(mpc.bus, 1);
20 % Number of lines.
21 num_L = size(mpc.branch, 1);
22
23 % Generate scenarios.
24 num_S = 10;
25 xi = zeros(num_W, num_S);
26 for w = 1:num_W
27     mu = 0.55;
28     sigma = 0.05;
29     a = (1 - mu)*mu^2/sigma^2 - mu;
30     b = (1 - mu)*a/mu;
31     pd = makedist('Beta', a, b);
32     xi(w, :) = random(pd, 1, num_S);
33 end
34
35 % Compute upper bound of wind power generation in each scenario.
36 xiP_W_plus = diag(wind(:, 2))*xi;
37
38 % Define upper bound of up- and down-regulation of conventional
39 % generators.
40 R_plus = mpc.gen(:, 9)*0.2;
41 R_minus = mpc.gen(:, 9)*0.2;
42
43 % Define upper and lower bound of real power output of conventional
44 % generators.
45 P_G_plus = mpc.gen(:, 9);
46 P_G_minus = mpc.gen(:, 10);
47
48 % Define demand.
49 P_D = mpc.bus(:, 3);
50
51 % Define incidence matrices.
52 AG = sparse(mpc.gen(:, 1), 1:num_G, ones(num_G, 1), num_B, num_G);
53 AW = sparse(wind(:, 1), 1:num_W, ones(num_W, 1), num_B, num_W);
54 AL = sparse([mpc.branch(:, 1); mpc.branch(:, 2)], [1:num_L, 1:num_L], ...
55     [-ones(num_L, 1); ones(num_L, 1)], num_B, num_L);
56

```

Appendix C MATLAB-Code

```
57 % Read reactances and invert them to build the susceptance-vector. Note
58 % that matpower uses degree as angle measure.
59 sus = 1./mpc.branch(:, 4)*360/(2*pi);
60 AL_tilde = transpose(AL*diag(sus));
61
62 % Define line capacities.
63 P_max = sus*0.25*pi/2;
64
65 % Define generator cost for a whole day, not for one hour as in MATPOWER.
66 C_FIX = mpc.gencost(:, 7)*24;
67 C_VAR = mpc.gencost(:, 6)*24;
68
69 % Define cost of up- and down-regulation of conventional generators.
70 C_R_plus = repelem(C_VAR*1.1, num_S);
71 C_R_minus = repelem(C_VAR*0.91, num_S);
72
73 % Define power purchase price at all wind farms.
74 C_PP = max(C_R_plus)*ones(num_W, 1);
75
76 % Define dimensions.
77 n = num_S*(num_W + 2*num_G + num_L + num_B) + 2*num_G;
78 m = 2*num_S*(num_W + 3*num_G + 2*num_L + num_B) + 2*(num_G + num_B);
79
80 % Prepare constraints for the algorithm's input.
81 B = sparse(m, n);
82 b = sparse(m, 1);
83
84 % Constraint (B.1.9)
85 first_row = 1; first_column = 1;
86 last_row = 2*num_W*num_S; last_column = num_W*num_S;
87 B(first_row:last_row, first_column:last_column) = ...
88     [-speye(num_W*num_S); speye(num_W*num_S)];
89 b(first_row:last_row) = [sparse(num_W*num_S, 1); xiP_W_plus(:)];
90
91 % Constraint (B.1.10)
92 first_row = last_row + 1; first_column = last_column + 1;
93 last_row = last_row + 2*num_G*num_S;
94 last_column = last_column + num_G*num_S;
95 B(first_row:last_row, first_column:last_column) = ...
96     [-speye(num_G*num_S); speye(num_G*num_S)];
97 b(first_row:last_row) = [sparse(num_G*num_S, 1); repmat(R_plus, num_S, 1)];
98
99 % Constraint (B.1.11)
100 first_row = last_row + 1; first_column = last_column + 1;
101 last_row = last_row + 2*num_G*num_S;
102 last_column = last_column + num_G*num_S;
103 B(first_row:last_row, first_column:last_column) = ...
104     [-speye(num_G*num_S); speye(num_G*num_S)];
105 b(first_row:last_row) = ...
106     [sparse(num_G*num_S, 1); repmat(R_minus, num_S, 1)];
107
108 % Constraints (B.1.12) and (B.1.13)
109 first_row = last_row + 1; first_column = num_W*num_S + 1;
110 last_row = last_row + 2*num_G*num_S; last_column = last_column + 2*num_G;
111 B(first_row:last_row, first_column:last_column) = ...
112     [speye(num_G*num_S), -speye(num_G*num_S), ...
113     repmat(speye(num_G), num_S, 1), repmat(-diag(P_G_plus), num_S, 1); ...
114     -speye(num_G*num_S), speye(num_G*num_S), ...
115     repmat(-speye(num_G), num_S, 1), repmat(diag(P_G_minus), num_S, 1)];
116
117
```

```

118 % Constraints (B.1.17) and (B.1.18)
119 first_row = last_row + 1; first_column = 1;
120 last_row = last_row + 2*num_B; last_column = last_column + num_L*num_S;
121 B(first_row:last_row, first_column:last_column) = ...
122     [repmat(AW, 1, num_S), repmat(AG, 1, num_S), repmat(-AG, 1, num_S), ...
123     AG, sparse(num_B, num_G), repmat(AL, 1, num_S); ...
124     repmat(-AW, 1, num_S), repmat(-AG, 1, num_S), repmat(AG, 1, num_S), ...
125     -AG, sparse(num_B, num_G), repmat(-AL, 1, num_S)];
126 b(first_row:last_row) = [P_D; -P_D];
127
128 % Constraints (B.1.19) and (B.1.20)
129 first_row = last_row + 1; first_column = last_column - num_L*num_S + 1;
130 last_row = last_row + 2*num_L*num_S;
131 B(first_row:last_row, first_column:end) = ...
132     [speye(num_L*num_S), kron(speye(num_S), -AL_tilde); ...
133     -speye(num_L*num_S), kron(speye(num_S), AL_tilde)];
134
135 % Constraint (B.1.21)
136 first_row = last_row + 1;
137 last_row = last_row + 2*num_L*num_S;
138 last_column = size(B, 2) - num_B*num_S;
139 B(first_row:last_row, first_column:last_column) = ...
140     [-speye(num_L*num_S); speye(num_L*num_S)];
141 b(first_row:last_row) = repmat(P_max, 2*num_S, 1);
142
143 % Constraint (B.1.22)
144 first_row = last_row + 1; first_column = first_column - num_G;
145 last_row = last_row + 2*num_G; last_column = last_column - num_L*num_S;
146 B(first_row:last_row, first_column:last_column) = ...
147     [-speye(num_G); speye(num_G)];
148 b(first_row:last_row) = [sparse(num_G, 1); ones(num_G, 1)];
149
150 % Constraint (B.1.23)
151 first_row = last_row + 1; first_column = last_column + num_L*num_S + 1;
152 B(first_row:end, first_column:end) = ...
153     [-speye(num_B*num_S); speye(num_B*num_S)];
154 b(first_row:end) = [sparse(num_B*num_S, 1); 2*pi*ones(num_B*num_S, 1)];
155
156 % Prepare objective function for the algorithm's input.
157 h = [sparse(num_W*num_S, 1); 1/num_S*C_R_plus; 1/num_S*C_R_minus; ...
158     C_VAR; C_FIX; sparse(num_S*(num_L + num_B), 1)];
159 D = sparse(num_S, n);
160 D(1:end, 1:num_W*num_S) = kron(speye(num_S), -C_PP');
161 v = xiP_W_plus'*C_PP;
162
163 %% Define missing parameters for the primal-dual algorithm.
164 beta = 0.9;
165 gamma = 1;
166 tau = 0.99/normest([D; B]);
167 sigma = tau;
168 x = zeros(n, 1);
169 y = zeros(num_S + m, 1);
170 eps = 1e-4;
171
172 %% Solve the problem with linprog.
173 [z, fval] = linprog([h', gamma, gamma/((1 - beta)*num_S)*ones(1, num_S)], ...
174     [B, zeros(size(B, 1), 1), zeros(size(B, 1), num_S); ...
175     D, -ones(num_S, 1), -eye(num_S)], [b; -v], ...
176     [], [], [-inf*ones(1, n + 1), zeros(1, num_S)], []);
177 x_linprog = z(1:n);
178

```

Appendix C MATLAB-Code

```
179 %% Solve the problem with the primal-dual algorithm.  
180 [x, ~] = PrimalDualAlgo(B, b, num_S, D, v, h, beta, gamma, tau, sigma, ...  
181     x, y, eps);
```

Declaration of Authorship

I, Sebastian Angerhausen, hereby certify that this thesis has been composed by me and is based on my own work, unless stated otherwise. No other person's work has been used without due acknowledgment in this thesis. All references and verbatim extracts have been quoted, and all sources of information, including graphs and data sets, have been specifically acknowledged.

Essen, May 28, 2018
